

Supplementary Materials

This supplementary document was prepared for the article “An Environmental Evaluation Framework for Planning and Monitoring of Nature Based Solutions for Sustainable Urban Management”. The article aims to establish an environmental assessment framework, which fosters the urban planning and implementation periods of Nature Based Solutions projects and forms a linkage between adaptation actions with urban sustainability policies by making use of monitoring data that enables predictive estimation of future scenarios.

NBS list is provided under related typology in the NBS classification (Table S1).

Table S1. NBS classification

Objects/shapes/physical projects				Strategies & Actions				
NBS Typology	On the ground	Water	On building structures	Urban green spaces management	Waste management	Protection and conservation strategies	Urban planning strategies	Monitoring
	Parks and Gardens	Natural and semi natural water bodies and hydrographic network	Green roofs	Direct human interventions				
	Structures associated to urban networks	Constructed wetlands and built structures for water management	Vertical structures: "Green walls & façades"	Use of fauna				
	Structures characterized by food and resources production							
	Ecological restoration							
	Choice of plants							
	Systems for erosion control							
Works on soil								

On the Ground

Table S2. System boundary infosheet for botanical gardens

Name of the NBS		Botanical gardens	
NBS Typology		Parks and gardens	
Description		A botanic garden is a public institution holding documented collections of well-tended living plants for the purposes of scientific research, conservation, display and education (Botanic Gardens Conservation International, BGCI). This distinguishes them from parks where plants are grown for public welfare only. Botanical gardens should have a complete documentation of their collections, control over collected plants and should demonstrate responsible management of their collections.	
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks ○ Capture atmospheric CO2 during natural lighting hours ○ Flood protection ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration ○ Reduce water supply due to evapotranspiration (benefit in regions prone to flooding but problem in arid or semi-arid regions) ○ Biodiversity ○ Increased soil surface ○ Soil organisms ○ Water holding capacity ○ Water remediation ○ Aesthetics ○ Increased soil organic matter 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Water demands
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ CO2 capture, lower atmospheric CO2 ○ Flood protection ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration ○ Reduce water supply due to evapotranspiration (benefit in regions prone to flooding but problem in arid or semi-arid regions) ○ Biodiversity ○ Increased soil surface ○ Soil organisms ○ Water holding capacity ○ Water remediation ○ Aesthetics ○ Reduction in urban heat island effect ○ Positive impact on energy consumption of surrounding buildings due to cooling effect ○ Indirect impact on energy efficiency of surrounding buildings in the neighbourhood increase in transportation demand as a result of recreational effect on the population (may lead to an increase in fossil fuel/primary energy consumption from the vehicles) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Energy and water demands
City scale			

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO ₂ sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O, N, C)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO ₂ eq/10 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq/100 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq per amount of biomass
Common air quality index	Air pollutants removed (O, N)	Direct capture by leaves, NO _x and PM capture	✓		µg/ m ³ , mg/ m ³ , kg/yr
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for cooling (N, C)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for cooling (N, C)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for maintenance (N, C)				
	Energy demand for water supply (N, C)				
Raw material efficiency	Water demand for irrigation (O, N, C)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Soil quality	Organic matter content of soil (O, N, C)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/m ³
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O, N)	Wastewater treatment, manufacturing of chemicals, transportation of chemicals	✓		m ³ /yr
	Surface runoff – not captured by stormwater sewers (O, N, C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Water scarcity	Water demand for irrigation (O, N, C)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
	Infiltration to groundwater (O, N, C)	Recharge of water into groundwater resources	✓	✓	m ³ /yr, in/h, mL/h

Table S3. System boundary infosheet for cemetery

Name of the NBS		Cemetery	
NBS Typology		Parks and gardens	
Description		Green cemeteries refer to burial ground often covered by lawns, trees and other ornamental plants. Although often underestimated, they are important components of NBS due to their number, size, habitat heterogeneity and habitat continuity. It is open to wide-range communities.	
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks, ○ Capture of atmospheric CO2 during natural lighting hours, ○ Reduce common air quality index background levels (Red_CAI_BGL); ○ Better air quality inside (Bet_AQ_in) - Mainly in Particle matter (PM) and less in NOx, ○ More infiltration surface, ○ Less runoff risks, ○ Groundwater replenishment, ○ Flood protection, ○ Water holding capacity, ○ Water remediation, ○ Increase in water resources due to water reclamation, ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration, ○ Certain tree species can reduce water supply due to evapotranspiration (benefit in regions prone to flooding but problem in arid or semi-arid regions), ○ Biodiversity, ○ Increased soil surface, ○ Soil organisms, ○ Aesthetics 		Increase in transportation demand should be considered as a result of recreational effect on the population (may lead to an increase in fossil fuel/primary energy consumption from the visitor vehicles)
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ CO2 sequestration, ○ Water reclamation, ○ Air pollutant filtration at larger scales 		
City scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ CO2 sequestration, ○ Air pollutant filtration, ○ Water reclamation 		

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO2 sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O, N, C)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO2 eq/10 yrs, kg CO2 eq/100 yrs, kg CO2 eq per amount of biomass
Avoided GHG emissions	GHG emissions released (O, N, C)	All GHG emitting processes including combustion, Energy generation, Transportation, Biogenic and anthropogenic	✓		kg CO2 eq/yr, kg CO2 eq/kg of product
Common air quality index	Air pollutants removed (O, N, C)	Direct capture by leaves, NOx and PM capture	✓	✓	µg/m3, mg/m3, kg/year
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for maintenance (O)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for water supply (O, N, C)				
	Energy demand for water treatment (O, N, C)				
Raw material efficiency	Chemicals used for water treatment (O)	Water treatment, Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing processes for chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		g/d, kg/d, kg/yr, ton/yr
	Fuel consumption for vehicles (O)	Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation, Fuel combustion	✓		L/100 km, L/km, m³/yr, MJ/yr, kg/d, kg/yr
	Herbicides – chemical (O)	Herbicide manufacturing, Herbicide transportation, Herbicide application	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Herbicides – organic (O)				
	Pesticides – chemical (O)	Pesticide manufacturing, Pesticide transport, Pesticide application	✓		
	Pesticides – organic (O)				
Water demand for irrigation (O)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m³/d, m³/yr	
Soil quality	Organic matter content of soil (O, N)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/ m³
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Surface runoff - not captured by stormwater sewers (O, N, C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m³/d, m³/yr
Water quality	Infiltration to groundwater (O, N, C)	Recharge of water into groundwater resources	✓	✓	m³/yr, in/h, mL/h
Water scarcity	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O, N, C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓	✓	m³/yr

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
	Water demand for irrigation (O)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr

Table S4. System boundary infosheet for flower fields

Name of the NBS		Flower fields	
NBS Typology		Parks and gardens	
Description			
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks ○ Capture atmospheric CO₂ during natural lighting hours ○ Flood protection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Water demand for irrigation 	
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration ○ Certain tree species can reduce water supply due to evapotranspiration (benefit in regions prone to flooding but problem in arid or semi-arid regions) ○ Biodiversity ○ Increased soil surface ○ Soil organisms ○ Water holding capacity ○ Water remediation ○ Aesthetics ○ Changes in local water stocks (temporal flows) 		
City scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks ○ Capture atmospheric CO₂ during natural lighting hours ○ Increased soil surface ○ Soil organisms ○ Water holding capacity ○ Water remediation ○ Aesthetics 		

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO ₂ sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O, N, C)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO ₂ eq/10 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq/100 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq per amount of biomass
Raw material efficiency	Water demand for irrigation (O, N)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Soil quality	Organic matter content of soil (O, N, C)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/m ³
Water quality	Eroded soil into waterbodies (O, N)	Erosion process		✓	kg/yr, t/yr, m ³ /yr

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Water scarcity	Infiltration to groundwater (O, N)	Recharge of water into groundwater resources	✓	✓	m ³ /yr, in/h, mL/h
	Water demand for irrigation (O, N)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr

Table S5. System boundary infosheet for hedge and planted fences

Name of the NBS		Hedge and planted fences	
NBS Typology		Parks and gardens	
Description			
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks, ○ Atmospheric CO2 capture during natural lighting hours ○ Increased soil surface, ○ Soil organisms, ○ Water holding capacity, ○ Water remediation, ○ Biodiversity, ○ Aesthetics 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Possible chemical use ○ Irrigation water consumption for maintenance of hedge and planted fences
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ CO2 capture, ○ Reduction in urban heat island effect (energy savings in surrounding buildings) 		
City scale			

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO2 sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O, N, C)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO2 eq/10 yrs, kg CO2 eq/100 yrs, kg CO2 eq per amount of biomass
Cumulative energy demands Energy efficiency	Energy demand for cooling (O, N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, Kwh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Raw material efficiency	Fertilizers – chemical (O, N)	Fertilizer manufacturing, Fertilizer transport, Fertilizer spreading	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Fertilizers – organic (O, N)				
	Herbicides – chemical (O, N)	Herbicide manufacturing, Herbicide transportation, Herbicide application			
	Herbicides – organic (O, N)				
	Insecticides – chemical (O, N)	Insecticide manufacturing, Insecticide transport, Insecticide application			
	Insecticides – organic (O, N)				

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
	Pesticides – chemical (O, N)	Pesticide manufacturing, Pesticide transport, Pesticide application			
	Pesticides – organic (O, N)				
	Water demand for irrigation (O)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /yr, m ³ /d
Water scarcity	Water demand for irrigation (O)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /yr, m ³ /d

Table S6. System boundary infosheet for heritage gardens

Name of the NBS		Heritage gardens	
NBS Typology		Parks and gardens	
Description		Heritage gardens are long-appreciated historic gardens with outstanding aesthetic or scientific values from the past, or they can also be a kind of private gardens that represent all societies at all times, with both tangible and intangible factors (Gao and Dietze-Schirdewahn, 2017).	
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks ○ Capture atmospheric CO₂ during natural lighting hours ○ More infiltration surface, less runoff risks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Groundwater replenishment ○ Flood protection ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration ○ Reduce water supply due to evapotranspiration (benefit in regions prone to flooding but problem in arid or semi-arid regions) ○ Biodiversity ○ Reduced erosion caused by water run-off ○ Reduced loss in soil matter by reduced wind speed ○ Increased soil organic matter ○ Reduction in urban heat island effect (energy savings at the city scale) ○ Possible rebound effect with transport associated with increasing number of visitors ○ Changes in water stocks (temporal flows) at larger scales (e.g. groundwater sources recharge) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Maintenance requirements (irrigation water and energy demand)
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Groundwater replenishment ○ Flood protection ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration ○ Reduce water supply due to evapotranspiration (benefit in regions prone to flooding but problem in arid or semi-arid regions) ○ Biodiversity ○ Reduced erosion caused by water run-off ○ Reduced loss in soil matter by reduced wind speed ○ Increased soil organic matter ○ Reduction in urban heat island effect (energy savings at the city scale) ○ Possible rebound effect with transport associated with increasing number of visitors ○ Changes in water stocks (temporal flows) at larger scales (e.g. groundwater sources recharge) 		
City scale	For only large historic gardens		

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO ₂ sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O, N, C)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO ₂ eq/10 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq/100 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq per amount of biomass
Common air quality index	Air pollutants removed (O, N)	Direct capture by leaves, NO _x and PM capture	✓		µg/ m ³ , mg/ m ³ , kg/yr
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for cooling (C)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for cooling (N, C)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for maintenance (N, C)				
	Energy demand for water supply (N, C)				

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Raw material efficiency	Infiltration to groundwater (O, N, C)	Recharge of water into groundwater resources	✓	✓	m ³ /yr, in/h, mL/h
	Water demand for irrigation (O, N, C)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Soil quality	Organic matter content of soil (O, N, C)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/m ³
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Stormwater avoided into sewer (O, N, C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		m ³ /yr
	Surface runoff – not captured by stormwater sewers (O, N, C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Water quality	Eroded soil into waterbodies (O, N, C)	Erosion process		✓	kg/yr, t/yr, m ³ /yr
Water scarcity	Infiltration to groundwater (O, N, C)	Recharge of water into groundwater resources	✓	✓	m ³ /yr, in/h, mL/h
	Water demand for irrigation (O, N, C)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr

Table S7. System boundary infosheet for large urban public parks

Name of the NBS		Large urban public parks	
NBS Typology		Parks and gardens	
Description		Large urban public parks refer to large green areas within a city with a variety of active and passive recreational facilities that meet the recreational and social needs of the residents and of visitors to the city. They are open to wide-range communities. In the optimal case they can be reached in 10-15 walking minutes by each resident.	
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks, ○ Capture of atmospheric CO2 during natural lighting hours, ○ Reduced CAI background levels (Red_CAI_BGL); ○ Better air quality inside (Bet_AQ_in) - Mainly in Particle matter (PM) and less in NOx, ○ More infiltration surface, ○ Less runoff risks, ○ Groundwater replenishment, ○ Flood protection, ○ Water holding capacity, ○ Water remediation, ○ Increase in water resources due to water reclamation, ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration, ○ Certain tree species can reduce water supply due to evapotranspiration (benefit in regions prone to flooding but problem in arid or semi-arid regions), ○ Biodiversity, ○ Increased soil surface, ○ Soil organisms, ○ Aesthetics, ○ Reduction in urban heat island effect, ○ Positive impact on energy consumption of surrounding buildings due to cooling effect, ○ Indirect impact on energy efficiency of surrounding buildings in the neighbourhood. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Increase in transportation demand should be considered as a result of recreational effect on the population (may lead to an increase in fossil fuel/primary energy consumption from the visitor vehicles) 	
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ CO2 sequestration, ○ Reduced cooling energy demands of neighbourhood buildings, ○ Water reclamation, ○ Air pollutant filtration at larger scales 		
City scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ CO2 sequestration, ○ Air pollutant filtration, ○ Water reclamation 		

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO2 sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O, N, C)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO2 eq/10 yrs, kg CO2 eq/100 yrs, kg CO2 eq per amount of biomass
Avoided GHG emissions	GHG emissions released (O, N, C)	All GHG emitting processes including combustion, Energy generation, Transportation, Biogenic and anthropogenic	✓		kg CO2 eq/yr, kg CO2 eq/kg of product
Building energy needs	Energy demand for cooling (O, N, C)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Common air quality index	Air pollutants released from vehicles (O, N, C)	Transportation activities, Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation	✓	✓	ug/ m ³ , mg/m ³ , mg/ m ³ /d, ug/ m ³ /d, kg/ m ³ /yr
	Air pollutants removed (O, N, C)	Direct capture by leaves, NOx and PM capture	✓	✓	μg/ m ³ , mg/ m ³ , kg/year
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for cooling (O, N, C)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for cooling (O, N, C)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for maintenance (O)				
	Energy demand for water supply (O, N, C)				
	Energy demand for water treatment (O, N, C)				
Raw material efficiency	Chemicals used for water treatment (O)	Water treatment, Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing processes for chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		g/d, kg/d, kg/yr, ton/yr
	Fuel consumption for vehicles (O)	Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation, Fuel combustion	✓		L/100 km, L/km, m ³ /yr, MJ/yr, kg/d, kg/yr
	Herbicides – chemical (O)	Herbicide manufacturing, Herbicide transportation, Herbicide application	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Herbicides – organic (O)				
	Pesticides – chemical (O)	Pesticide manufacturing, Pesticide transport, Pesticide application	✓		
	Pesticides – organic (O)				
Water demand for irrigation (O)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr	

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
	Water for maintenance (O)	Pumping operations, Water treatment if necessary			
Soil quality	Organic matter content of soil (O, N)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/ m ³
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O, N, C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		m ³ /yr
	Surface runoff - not captured by stormwater sewers (O, N, C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Water quality	Infiltration to groundwater (O, N, C)	Recharge of water into groundwater resources	✓	✓	m ³ /yr, in/h, mL/h
Water scarcity	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O, N, C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓	✓	m ³ /yr
	Water demand for irrigation (O)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
	Water for maintenance (O)	Pumping operations, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr

Table S8. System boundary infosheet for lawns

Name of the NBS		Lawns	
NBS Typology		Parks and gardens	
Description	A lawn is an area land covered with soil, planted with grasses and other durable plants such as clover, which are maintained at a short height. Common characteristics of a lawn are that it is composed only of grass species, it is subject to weed and pest control, it is subject to practices aimed at maintaining its green colour (e.g., watering), and it is regularly mowed to ensure an acceptable length, although these characteristics are not binding as a definition. Lawns are used around houses, apartments, commercial buildings and offices, and they can also be found in urban parks. Lawns have an important role in daily life of inhabitants, through their aesthetic and recreational value. Proper lawn maintenance plays a crucial part in any landscape design.		
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	N/A		N/A
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks ○ Capture atmospheric CO2 during natural lighting hours ○ More infiltration surface ○ Less runoff risks ○ Groundwater replenishment ○ Flood protection ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration ○ Reduce water supply due to evapotranspiration (benefit in regions prone to flooding but problem in arid or semi-arid regions) ○ Biodiversity ○ Increased soil surface soil organisms, water holding capacity, water remediation ○ Aesthetics ○ Reduction in urban heat island effect ○ Positive impact on energy consumption of surrounding buildings due to cooling effect ○ Indirect impact on energy efficiency of surrounding buildings in the neighbourhood biodiversity ○ Changes in local water stocks (temporal flows) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Fertilizers usage ○ Energy demand and water demand ○ Possible rebound effect with transport associated with increasing number of visitors
City scale	N/A		N/A

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO ₂ sequestration	Carbon sequestered (N)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO ₂ eq/10 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq/100 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq per amount of biomass
Avoided GHG emissions	GHG emissions released (N)	All GHG emitting processes including combustion, Energy generation, Transportation, Biogenic and anthropogenic	✓		kg CO ₂ eq/yr, kg CO ₂ eq/kg of product
Common air quality index	Air pollutants released from vehicles (N)	Transportation activities, Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation	✓		mg/ m ³ , ug/m ³ , mg/ m ³ /d, ug/ m ³ /d, kg/ m ³ /yr
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for cooling (N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for cooling (N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for maintenance (N)				
	Energy demand for water supply (N)				
Raw material efficiency	Fertilizer-chemical (N)	Fertilizer manufacturing, Fertilizer transport, Fertilizer spreading	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Fertilizer-organic (N)				
	Water demand for irrigation (N)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Soil quality	Organic matter content of soil (N)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/m ³
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (N)	Wastewater treatment, manufacturing of chemicals, transportation of chemicals	✓		m ³ /yr
	Surface runoff – not captured by stormwater sewers (N)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Water scarcity	Water demand for irrigation (N)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
	Infiltration to groundwater (N)	Recharge of water into groundwater resources	✓	✓	m ³ /yr, in/h, mL/h

Table S9. System boundary infosheet for pocket gardens

Name of the NBS		Pocket gardens	
NBS Typology		Parks and gardens	
Description	Small and compact park-like areas or small gardens around and between buildings vegetated by ornamental trees, grass and other types of plants (perennial, annual plants, herbaceous), publicly accessible (Nordh and Østby, 2013; Braquinho et al. 2015). They can be tucked into and scattered throughout the urban fabric as stepping stones for species (Ramirez and Zuria, 2011, Konijnendijk et al., 2013). Because of its size it usually does not provide opportunities for great physical activity, but their functions include small event space, play areas for children, spaces for relaxing, meeting friends and other social activities, taking lunch outdoor and to some extent fill the need for peoples every day contact with nature (Dunnett et al. 2002; Cohen et al., 2014; Armano, 2017; Bitterman N. and Simonov E., 2017; Peschardt 2014).		
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks ○ Capture atmospheric CO2 during natural lighting hours ○ Flood protection ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration ○ Certain tree species can reduce water supply due to evapotranspiration (benefit in regions prone to flooding but problem in arid or semi-arid regions) ○ Biodiversity ○ Increased soil surface ○ Soil organisms, water holding capacity ○ Water remediation ○ Biodiversity ○ Aesthetics ○ Changes in local water stocks (temporal flows) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Water demand
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Reduction in urban heat island effect ○ Positive impact on energy consumption of surrounding buildings due to cooling effect ○ Indirect impact on energy efficiency of surrounding buildings in the neighbourhood ○ Increased soil surface ○ Soil organisms ○ Water holding capacity ○ Water remediation ○ Biodiversity ○ Aesthetics ○ Changes in water stocks (temporal flows) at larger scales (e.g. groundwater sources recharge) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Increase in transportation demand as a result of recreational effect on the population (may lead to an increase in fossil fuel/primary energy consumption from the vehicles) ○ Energy demand for maintenance, water demand
City scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Changes in water stocks (temporal flows) at larger scales (e.g. groundwater sources recharge) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Water demand

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO ₂ sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO ₂ eq/10 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq/100 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq per amount of biomass
Avoided GHG emissions	GHG emissions released (O)	All GHG emitting processes including combustion, Energy generation, Transportation, Biogenic and anthropogenic	✓		kg CO ₂ eq/yr, kg CO ₂ eq/kg of product
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for cooling (N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for cooling (N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for maintenance (N)				
Raw material efficiency	Fuel consumption for vehicles (N)	Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation, Fuel combustion	✓		L/100 km, L/km, m ³ /yr, MJ/yr
	Water demand for irrigation (O, N, C)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Soil quality	Organic matter content of soil (O, N)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/m ³
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Surface runoff – not captured by stormwater sewers (O)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Water scarcity	Water demand for irrigation (O, N, C)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr

Table S10. System boundary infosheet for private gardens

Name of the NBS		Private gardens	
NBS Typology		Parks and gardens	
Description	The private garden is a type of Urban Green Spaces Areas in immediate vicinity of private (privately owned or rented) houses, cultivated mainly for ornamental purposes and/or non-commercial food production (Cvejić et al. 2015; Dewaelheyns et al., 2018). Gardens offer possibilities to sustain and improve ecological and social qualities in people's everyday environment, and they have a potential to support a wide range of ecosystem services (Loram et al., 2008; Tappert et al., 2018). A key element is that the resident/s have autonomy over the garden, so we exclude the open green spaces and communal gardens (with management by committee, local authority), smaller public parks and gardens (pocket gardens) (Cameron et al., 2012). Depending on age and location of cities, domestic gardens contribute to a wide range (between 10 and 36%) of the total urban area (Loram et al, 2007; Mathieu et al., 2007).		
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Reduction in urban heat island effect (energy savings in surrounding buildings) ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration ○ Food production 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Fertilizers usage ○ Energy demands ○ Increased water utilization in summer ○ Possible rebound effect with transport associated with increasing number of visitors 	
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks ○ Capture atmospheric CO2 during natural lighting hours ○ Flood protection ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration ○ Reduce water supply due to evapotranspiration (benefit in regions prone to flooding but problem in arid or semi-arid regions) ○ Biodiversity ○ Food production ○ Reduction in urban heat island effect (energy savings in surrounding buildings) ○ Changes in local water stocks (temporal flows) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Water contamination 	
City scale	N/A		N/A

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO ₂ sequestration	Carbon sequestered (N)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO ₂ eq/10 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq/100 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq per amount of biomass
Avoided GHG emissions	GHG emissions released (O)	All GHG emitting processes including combustion, Energy generation, Transportation, Biogenic and anthropogenic	✓		kg CO ₂ eq/yr, kg CO ₂ eq/kg of product
Common air quality index	Air pollutants released from vehicles (O)	Transportation activities, Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation	✓		mg/ m ³ , ug/ m ³ , mg/ m ³ /d, ug/ m ³ /d, kg/ m ³ /yr
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for cooling (O, N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for maintenance (O)				
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for cooling (O)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for maintenance (O)				
	Energy demand for water supply (O)				
Raw material efficiency	Fertilizer-chemical (O)	Fertilizer manufacturing, Fertilizer transport, Fertilizer spreading	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Fertilizer-organic (O)	Fertilizer manufacturing, Fertilizer transport, Fertilizer spreading	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Food supply – of plant origin (O, N)	Urban agriculture, Transportation of produce, Fuel consumption, Irrigation processes, Production and transportation of agricultural chemicals, Consumption of resources for maintenance, Conventional farming activities	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Water demand for irrigation (O)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Soil quality	Organic matter content of soil (N)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/m ³
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (N)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		m ³ /yr
	Surface runoff – not captured by stormwater sewers (N)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Water quality	Water pollutants released (N)	All processes creating water pollutants	✓		mg/L, ug/L, kg/ m ³ , kg/L
Water scarcity	Infiltration to groundwater (O, N)	Recharge of water into groundwater resources	✓	✓	m ³ /yr, in/h, mL/h
	Water demand for irrigation (O)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr

Table S11. System boundary infosheet for public urban green spaces-public urban green spaces with specific uses-take into account the distribution of public green spaces through the city

Public urban green spaces Public urban green spaces with specific uses Take into account the distribution of public green spaces through the city		
Name of the NBS		Parks and gardens
NBS Typology		Parks and gardens
Description	This NBS is an urban green space with specific uses in densely built-up urban areas that loosens urban fabric. The patterns of usage of public spaces – places and squares – are to a large extent set by cultural values and habits as well as social status, sex et cetera that rather change in time. People in different countries have different attitudes to public areas and the actual settings reflect such differences in needs, demands and practices. Americans and Brits tend to spend their lunch in the small green areas in front of their offices whereas people in Central Europe use parks rather as weekend recreation and rarely compared to the situation in Western Europe. Northerners spend their times more actively whereas people from the south opt rather for resting. In some areas, open green spaces are seen as threats as it gives shelter to undesired activities and functions, consequently, they are fenced and closed for the night. The patterns also change with time, especially in East-Central Europe. During communism and in the decades after, people tended to use less such facilities in urbanised areas as social gatherings used to be regarded as an act against the power. Moreover, people had strong ‘stayinghome’ attitudes (Konrád-Szelényi, 1969), also favoured by the communist system, compared to the ‘going-out’ attitudes of periods preceding communist rule and present times.	
Narrative impacts		Positive
		Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks, ○ Capture of atmospheric CO₂ during natural lighting hours, ○ Reduced common air quality index background levels (Red_CAI_BGL); ○ Better air quality inside (Bet_AQ_in) - Mainly in Particle matter (PM) and less in NO_x, ○ More infiltration surface, ○ Less runoff risks, ○ Groundwater replenishment, ○ Flood protection, ○ Water holding capacity, ○ Water remediation, ○ Increase in water resources due to water reclamation, ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration, ○ Certain tree species can reduce water supply due to evapotranspiration (benefit in regions prone to flooding but problem in arid or semi-arid regions), ○ Biodiversity, ○ Increased soil surface, ○ Soil organisms, ○ Aesthetics, ○ Reduction in urban heat island effect, ○ Positive impact on energy consumption of surrounding buildings due to cooling effect, ○ Indirect impact on energy efficiency of surrounding buildings in the neighbourhood. 	Increase in transportation demand should be considered as a result of recreational effect on the population (may lead to an increase in fossil fuel/primary energy consumption from the visitor vehicles)
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ CO₂ sequestration, ○ Reduced cooling energy demands of neighbourhood buildings, ○ Water reclamation, ○ Air pollutant filtration at larger scales 	

Public urban green spaces Public urban green spaces with specific uses Take into account the distribution of public green spaces through the city	
Parks and gardens	
Name of the NBS	
NBS Typology	
City scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ CO2 sequestration, ○ Air pollutant filtration, ○ Water reclamation

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO2 sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O, N, C)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO2 eq/10 yrs, kg CO2 eq/100 yrs, kg CO2 eq per amount of biomass
Avoided GHG emissions	GHG emissions released (O, N, C)	All GHG emitting processes including combustion, Energy generation, Transportation, Biogenic and anthropogenic	✓		kg CO2 eq/yr, kg CO2 eq/kg of product
Building energy needs	Energy demand for cooling (O, N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Common air quality index	Air pollutants released from vehicles (O, N, C)	Transportation activities, Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation	✓	✓	ug/m3, mg/m3, mg/m3/d, ug/m3/d, kg/m3/yr
	Air pollutants removed (O, N, C)	Direct capture by leaves, NOx and PM capture	✓	✓	µg/m3, mg/m3, kg/year
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for cooling (O, N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for cooling (O, N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for maintenance (O)				
	Energy demand for water supply (O, N, C)				
	Energy demand for water treatment (O, N, C)				
Raw material efficiency	Chemicals used for water treatment (O)	Water treatment, Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing processes for chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		g/d, kg/d, kg/yr, ton/yr
	Fuel consumption for vehicles (O)	Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation, Fuel combustion	✓		L/100 km, L/km, m3/yr, MJ/yr, kg/d, kg/yr

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
	Herbicides – chemical (O)	Herbicide manufacturing, Herbicide transportation, Herbicide application	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Herbicides – organic (O)				
	Pesticides – chemical (O)	Pesticide manufacturing, Pesticide transport, Pesticide application			
	Pesticides – organic (O)				
	Water demand for irrigation (O)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m3/d, m3/yr
	Water for maintenance (O)	Pumping operations, Water treatment if necessary			
Soil quality	Organic matter content of soil (O, N)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/m3
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Surface runoff - not captured by stormwater sewers (O, N, C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m3/d, m3/yr
Water quality	Infiltration to groundwater (O, N, C)	Recharge of water into groundwater resources	✓	✓	m3/yr, in/h, mL/h
Water scarcity	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O, N, C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓	✓	m3/yr
	Water demand for irrigation (O)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m3/d, m3/yr
	Water for maintenance (O)	Pumping operations, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m3/d, m3/yr

Table S12. System boundary infosheet for single trees

Name of the NBS		Single trees	
NBS Typology		Parks and gardens	
Description	An urban single tree in a NBS context is an individually standing tree (independently of its age), which is recorded and managed independently from the other elements of the surrounding vegetation (e.g. trees of a nearby park). A single tree stands on an extended unsealed surface (in contrast to street trees). From the point of view of most of the urban challenges, small trees (<~2m) are functioning similarly to hedges and shrubs, thus they can be included in those categories.		
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	N/A		N/A
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks ○ Capture atmospheric CO₂ during natural lighting hours ○ Flood protection ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration ○ Reduce water supply due to evapotranspiration (benefit in regions prone to flooding but problem in arid or semi-arid regions) ○ Biodiversity ○ Interception of stormwater and reduced run-off ○ Reduced erosion caused by water run-off ○ Reduction in urban heat island effect ○ Positive impact on energy consumption of surrounding buildings due to cooling effect ○ Indirect impact on energy efficiency of surrounding buildings in the neighbourhood biodiversity ○ Potential for reduced energy need due to water reclamation (link between water and energy) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Energy and water demand 	
City scale	N/A		N/A

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO ₂ sequestration	Carbon sequestered (N)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO ₂ eq/10 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq/100 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq per amount of biomass
Building energy needs	Energy demand for cooling (N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Common air quality index	Air pollutants removed (N)	Direct capture by leaves, NO _x and PM captures	✓		µg/ m ³ , mg/ m ³ , kg/year
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for cooling (N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for cooling (N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for maintenance (N)				
	Energy demand for water supply (N)				
Raw material efficiency	Infiltration to groundwater (N)	Recharge of water into groundwater resources	✓	✓	m ³ /yr, in/h, mL/h
	Water demand for irrigation (N)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Soil quality	Eroded soil into waterbodies (N)	Erosion process		✓	kg/yr, t/yr, m ³ /yr
	Organic matter content of soil (N)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/m ³
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (N)	Wastewater treatment, manufacturing of chemicals, transportation of chemicals	✓		m ³ /yr
	Surface runoff – not captured by stormwater sewers (N)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Water scarcity	Infiltration to groundwater (N)	Recharge of water into groundwater resources	✓	✓	m ³ /yr, in/h, mL/h
	Water demand for irrigation (N)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr

Table S13. System boundary infosheet for vegetated pergolas

Name of the NBS		Vegetated pergolas	
NBS Typology		Parks and gardens	
Description	The use of garden structures in combination with plants has a long tradition and goes back to the ancient times to the gardens of Mesopotamia, Egypt, Persia and China (app. 2000-500 BC). Over time a variety of terminology has formed and a clear definition of the different structures is not that easy all time. Nevertheless, it's always about a kind of built structure which uses pillars, beams and lattices in different materials and compositions to create a growing assistance for vegetation (Hansen 2010).		
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks, ○ Capture of atmospheric CO2 during natural lighting hours, ○ Food production, ○ Potential reduced energy demand at object scale by air cooling effect (or when used in combination w/solar panels), ○ Reduction in urban heat island effect: reduces energy needs for cooling 		Any increase in energy demand due to maintenance requirements should be investigated.
Neighbourhood scale	N/A		N/A
City scale	N/A		N/A

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO2 sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO2 eq/10 yrs, kg CO2 eq/100 yrs, kg CO2 eq per amount of biomass
Avoided GHG emissions	GHG emissions avoided (O)	All GHG emitting processes including combustion, Energy generation, Transportation	✓	✓	kg CO2 eq/yr, kg CO2 eq/kg of product
Building energy needs	Energy demand for cooling (O)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Common air quality index	Air pollutants removed (O)	Direct capture by leaves, NOx and PM capture	✓	✓	µg/m3, mg/m3, kg/year
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for cooling (O)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for cooling (O)				
Per capita food production variability	Food supply – of plant origin (O)	Urban agriculture, Transportation of produce, Fuel consumption, Irrigation processes, Production and transportation of agricultural chemicals, Consumption of resources for maintenance, Conventional farming activities	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Raw material efficiency	Food supply – of plant origin (O)	Urban agriculture, Transportation of produce, Fuel consumption, Irrigation processes, Production and transportation of agricultural chemicals, Consumption of resources for maintenance, Conventional farming activities	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Fuel consumption for vehicles (O)	Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation, Fuel combustion	✓		L/100 km, L/km, m ³ /yr, MJ/yr, kg/d, kg/yr

Table S14. System boundary infosheet for woods

Name of the NBS		Woods	
NBS Typology		Parks and gardens	
Description	Woods are groups of trees (or areas of land, covered with trees), which are independent from a bigger urban park or other public urban green space. Woods do not have any special function in the life of urban inhabitants (botanical exhibition, cemetery, etc.), and may also contain smaller trees, e.g. in a growing phase. The number of adjacent trees can help to differentiate from single trees, while parks often have special status in local urban environmental management or spatial planning (which is not the case for woods).		
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Balanced micro climate, ○ Reduction in urban heat island effect, ○ Indirect positive impact on energy consumption of surrounding buildings due to cooling effect, 		
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Reduce common air quality index background levels (Red_CAI_BGL), ○ Better air quality inside (Bet_AQ_in) - PM and NOx, ○ Carbon savings ○ More infiltration surface, ○ Groundwater replenishment, ○ Interception of stormwater ○ Reduced run-off, ○ Natural barrier, ○ Reduced erosion caused by water run-off, ○ Efficient utilization of rainwater, ○ Soil regeneration, ○ Increase in soil organic matter, ○ Biodiversity 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ wood for heating or utilization as a construction material ○ Pesticides and herbicides for maintenance
City scale			

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO2 sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O, N)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO2 eq/10 yrs, kg CO2 eq/100 yrs, kg CO2 eq per amount of biomass
Avoided GHG emissions	GHG emissions avoided (O, N)	All GHG emitting processes including combustion, Energy generation, Transportation	✓	✓	kg CO2 eq/yr, kg CO2 eq/kg of product
Building energy needs	Energy demand for cooling (O, N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Common air quality index	Air pollutants removed (O, N)	Direct capture by leaves, NOx and PM capture	✓	✓	µg/m3, mg/m3, kg/year

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for cooling (O, N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for cooling (O, N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Peak flow variation	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O, N)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals			m3/yr
	Surface runoff - not captured by stormwater sewers (O, N)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m3/d, m3/yr
Raw material efficiency	Infiltration to groundwater (O, N)	Recharge of water into groundwater resources	✓	✓	m3/yr, in/h, mL/h
	Herbicides – chemical (O)	Herbicide manufacturing, Herbicide transportation, Herbicide application	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Herbicides – organic (O)				
	Pesticides – chemical (O)	Pesticide manufacturing, Pesticide transport, Pesticide application	✓		
	Pesticides – organic (O)				
	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O, N, C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓	✓	m3/yr
Surface runoff - not captured by stormwater sewers (O, N)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m3/d, m3/yr	
Soil quality	Organic matter content of soil (O, N)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/m3
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O, N)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓	✓	m3/yr
	Surface runoff - not captured by stormwater sewers (O, N)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m3/d, m3/yr
Water quality	Infiltration to groundwater (O, N)	Recharge of water into groundwater resources	✓	✓	m3/yr, in/h, mL/h

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Water scarcity	Infiltration to groundwater (O, N)	Recharge of water into groundwater resources	✓	✓	m ³ /yr, in/h, mL/h
	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O, N, C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓	✓	m ³ /yr
	Surface runoff - not captured by stormwater sewers (O, N)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr

On the Ground

Table S15. System boundary infosheet for grass tram tracks

Name of the NBS		Grass tram tracks	
NBS Typology		Structures associated to urban networks	
Description		This NBS Type is about green tram tracks which are unsealed and greened with grasses or sedum species and thus achieve several valuable ecological, economic and urban design benefits.	
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks ○ Capture atmospheric CO2 during natural lighting hours ○ Flood protection ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration ○ Certain tree species can reduce water supply due to evapotranspiration (benefit in regions prone to flooding but Problem in arid or semi-arid regions) ○ Biodiversity ○ Increased soil surface ○ Soil organisms ○ Water holding capacity ○ Water remediation ○ Aesthetics 		
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks ○ Capture atmospheric CO2 during natural lighting hours ○ Flood protection ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration ○ Certain tree species can reduce water supply due to evapotranspiration (benefit in regions prone to flooding but Problem in arid or semi-arid regions) ○ Biodiversity ○ Increased soil surface ○ Soil organisms ○ Water holding capacity ○ Water remediation ○ Aesthetics ○ Reduction in urban heat island effect ○ Positive impact on energy consumption of surrounding buildings due to cooling effect ○ Decrease in irrigation needs due to water reclamation (link between water and energy) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Water and energy demands
City scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks ○ Capture atmospheric CO2 during natural lighting hours ○ Increased soil surface ○ Soil organisms ○ Water holding capacity 		

Name of the NBS	Grass tram tracks	
NBS Typology	Structures associated to urban networks	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Water remediation ○ Aesthetics ○ Reduction in urban heat island effect ○ Positive impact on energy consumption of surrounding buildings due to cooling effect 	

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO ₂ sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O, N, C)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO ₂ eq/10 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq/100 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq per amount of biomass
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for cooling (N, C)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for cooling (N, C)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for water supply (N, C)				
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Surface runoff not captured by stormwater sewers (O, N)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O, N)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		m ³ /yr
Raw material efficiency	Water demand for irrigation (O, N)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Water scarcity	Water demand for irrigation (O, N)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O, N)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		m ³ /yr

Table S16. System boundary infosheet for green strips

Name of the NBS		Green strips	
NBS Typology		Structures associated to urban networks	
Description		Green or vegetated strips are greened surfaces next to impermeable surface, typically beside roads and railways. They are typically covered with grasses, shrubs and/or small trees. Due to road safety they have to be cut regularly (MARTÍNEZ 2016).	
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks ○ Capture atmospheric CO2 during natural lighting hours ○ Flood protection ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration ○ Certain tree species can reduce water supply due to evapotranspiration (benefit in regions prone to flooding but problem in arid or semi-arid regions) ○ Biodiversity ○ Reduction of runoff water volumes ○ Increased soil quality ○ Soil organisms ○ Water holding capacity ○ Water remediation ○ Aesthetics 		N/A
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks ○ Capture atmospheric CO2 during natural lighting hours ○ Flood protection ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration ○ Certain tree species can reduce water supply due to evapotranspiration (benefit in regions prone to flooding but problem in arid or semi-arid regions) ○ Biodiversity ○ Reduction of runoff water volumes ○ Increased soil quality ○ Soil organisms ○ Water holding capacity ○ Water remediation ○ Aesthetics ○ Reduction in urban heat island effect ○ Positive impact on energy consumption of surrounding buildings due to cooling effect ○ Indirect impact on energy efficiency of surrounding buildings in the neighbourhood ○ Potential for reduced energy need due to water reclamation (link between water and energy) 		N/A
City scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks ○ Capture atmospheric CO2 during natural lighting hours ○ Increased soil quality ○ Soil organisms 		N/A

Name of the NBS	Green strips	
NBS Typology	Structures associated to urban networks	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Water holding capacity ○ Water remediation ○ Aesthetics ○ Reduction in urban heat island effect ○ Positive impact on energy consumption of surrounding buildings due to cooling effect ○ Indirect impact on energy efficiency of surrounding buildings in the neighbourhood ○ Potential for reduced energy need due to water reclamation (link between water and energy) 	

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO ₂ sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O, N, C)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO ₂ eq/10 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq/100 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq per amount of biomass
Common air quality index	Air pollutants removed (O, N, C)	Direct capture by leaves, NO _x and PM capture	✓		µg/ m ³ , mg/ m ³ , kg/yr
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for cooling (N, C)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Efficiency of valorisation as a result of recycling process	Waste recycled (O)	Recycling processes, Incineration process, Composting, Energy generation, Water pumping and treatment	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for cooling (N, C)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Raw material efficiency	Other resource (O, N, C)	All relevant processes producing or consuming resources not specified elsewhere in the list	✓	✓	kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Soil quality	Organic matter content of soil (O, N, C)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/m ³
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Stormwater avoided into sewer (O, N)	Wastewater treatment, manufacturing of chemicals, transportation of chemicals	✓		m ³ /yr
	Surface runoff – not captured by stormwater sewers (O, N)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Water quality	Eroded soil into waterbodies	Erosion process		✓	kg/yr, t/yr, m ³ /yr

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Water scarcity	Water supply from alternative sources than supply system	Pumping, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m3/d, m3/yr

Table S17. System boundary infosheet for green waterfront city

Name of the NBS		Green waterfront city	
NBS Typology		Structures associated to urban networks	
Description	Due to climate change sea level is rising and thus brings challenges for local governments with coastal access and communities - waterfronts. Waterfronts are a space, parts or a district of a city with access to water, often grown historically without an overall plan and thus nowadays often revitalised. It is not only about a sea access, it also can be direct access to lakes, rivers or similar larger water elements. Beside sea level rising, extreme weather events are increasing too and thus storm water management is getting a more relevant issue. The implementation of a green waterfront city provides opportunities to restore and protect coastal ecosystems and to protect coastal communities by same time having a wide range of benefits, especially regarding recreation. By the same time, these complex urban processes are often challenged by social challenges like gentrification and need in general an overall strategy.		
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks ○ Capture atmospheric CO2 during natural lighting hours ○ Flood protection ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration ○ Certain tree species can reduce water supply due to evapotranspiration (benefit in regions prone to flooding but problem in arid or semi-arid regions) ○ Biodiversity ○ Increased soil quality ○ Soil organisms ○ Water holding capacity ○ Water remediation ○ Aesthetics 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Energy demand for construction
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Flood protection ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration ○ Certain tree species can reduce water supply due to evapotranspiration (benefit in regions prone to flooding but problem in arid or semi-arid regions) ○ Biodiversity ○ Increased soil quality ○ Soil organisms ○ Water holding capacity ○ Water remediation ○ Aesthetics 		
City scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Flood protection ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration ○ Certain tree species can reduce water supply due to evapotranspiration (benefit in regions prone to flooding but problem in arid or semi-arid regions) ○ Biodiversity ○ Increased soil quality ○ Soil organisms ○ Water holding capacity 		

Name of the NBS		Green waterfront city	
NBS Typology		Structures associated to urban networks	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Water remediation ○ Aesthetics ○ Reduction in urban heat island effect ○ Positive impact on energy consumption of surrounding buildings due to cooling effect ○ Potential for reduced energy need due to water reclamation (link between water and energy) ○ Decrease in irrigation needs due to water reclamation (link between water and energy) 		

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO ₂ sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O, N, C)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO ₂ eq/10 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq/100 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq per amount of biomass
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for cooling (C)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for construction (O)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for cooling (C)				
	Energy demand for water supply (C)				
Raw material efficiency	Water supply from alternative sources than supply system (O, N, C)	Pumping, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Soil quality	Organic matter content of soil (O, N, C)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/m ³
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Surface runoff – not captured by stormwater sewers (O, N, C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /day, m ³ /yr

Table S18. System boundary infosheet for planted car parks

Name of the NBS		Planted car parks	
NBS Typology		Structures associated to urban networks	
Description	Greened parking lots is the greened version of a parking plot. Compared to traditional solutions, they use vegetation for storm water management and to address several further urban challenges. Traditional solutions gain the impacts of Urban Heat Islands (UHI), can cause water quality and storm water issues. They are characterized with grass and/or herb plantings.		
Narrative impacts	Positive	Negative	
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks ○ Capture atmospheric CO2 during natural lighting hours ○ Flood protection ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration ○ Certain tree species can reduce water supply due to evapotranspiration (benefit in regions prone to flooding but problem in arid or semi-arid regions) ○ Biodiversity ○ Reduced runoff water volume ○ Increased water infiltration ○ Reduced flood effect ○ Substrate/drainage can be recycled ○ Increased soil surface ○ Habitat for organisms ○ Reduction in urban heat island effect because of the cooling effect of evapotranspiration ○ Increased green areas ○ Enhanced water retention capacity 		
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks ○ Capture atmospheric CO2 during natural lighting hours ○ Flood protection ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration ○ Certain tree species can reduce water supply due to evapotranspiration (benefit in regions prone to flooding but problem in arid or semi-arid regions) ○ Biodiversity ○ Habitat for organisms ○ Reduction in urban heat island effect because of the cooling effect of evapotranspiration ○ Increased green areas ○ Enhanced water retention capacity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Energy demand 	
City scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks ○ Capture atmospheric CO2 during natural lighting hours ○ Increased soil surface ○ Biodiversity ○ Habitat for organisms 		

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO ₂ sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O, N, C)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO ₂ eq/10 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq/100 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq per amount of biomass
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for cooling (N, C)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for construction (N, C)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Raw material efficiency	Water supply from alternative sources than supply system (O, N)	Pumping, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Soil quality	Organic matter content of soil (O, N, C)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/m ³
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O)	Wastewater treatment, manufacturing of chemicals, transportation of chemicals			m ³ /yr
	Surface runoff – not captured by stormwater sewers (O)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Water quality	Eroded soil into waterbodies (O, N)	Erosion process		✓	kg/yr, t/yr, m ³ /yr
Water scarcity	Water supply from alternative sources than supply system (O, N)	Pumping, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr

Table S19. System boundary infosheet for street trees

Name of the NBS		Street trees	
NBS Typology		Structures associated to urban networks	
Description	A street tree is any tree growing within the public-right-of-way and is thus managed by the city. Typically, they are located along sidewalks and/or streets. This NBS type is one of the most important part in the urban green network. This effective and important implementation has multiple visual and physical impacts on quality of life in urban areas. They provide shading and cooling through transpiration and evapotranspiration and thus reduce temperature. Compared to a single tree, street trees are planted in groups like a canopy road/avenue/boulevard. Trees need water and oxygen to survive and be productive, thus the water-oxygen-balance is of high importance for a successful tree growing. Street trees have e.g. lower water use compared to single trees, because there are not that exposed. But the requirements for street trees within the urban space are often limited available.		
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Reduced common air quality index background levels (Red_CAI_BGL); ○ Better air quality inside (Bet_AQ_in) - Mainly in Particle matter (PM) and less in NOx, ○ More infiltration surface, ○ Less runoff risks, ○ Groundwater replenishment, ○ Flood protection, ○ Water holding capacity, ○ Water remediation, ○ Increase in water resources due to water reclamation, ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration, ○ Certain tree species can reduce water supply due to evapotranspiration (benefit in regions prone to flooding but problem in arid or semi-arid regions), ○ Biodiversity, ○ Aesthetics, ○ Reduction in urban heat island effect, ○ Positive impact on energy consumption of surrounding buildings due to cooling effect, ○ Indirect impact on energy efficiency of surrounding buildings in the neighbourhood. 		
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ CO2 sequestration, ○ Reduced cooling energy demands of neighbourhood buildings, ○ Water reclamation, ○ Air pollutant filtration at larger scales 		
City scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ CO2 sequestration, ○ Air pollutant filtration, ○ Water reclamation 		

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO2 sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O, N, C)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO2 eq/10 yrs, kg CO2 eq/100 yrs, kg CO2 eq per amount of biomass

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Building energy needs	Energy demand for cooling (O, N, C)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Common air quality index	Air pollutants removed (O, N, C)	Direct capture by leaves, NOx and PM capture	✓	✓	µg/m3, mg/m3, kg/year
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for cooling (O, N, C)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for cooling (O, N, C)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for water supply (O, N, C)				
	Energy demand for water treatment (O, N, C)				
Raw material efficiency	Chemicals used for water treatment (O)	Water treatment, Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing processes for chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		g/d, kg/d, kg/yr, ton/yr
	Herbicides – chemical (O)	Herbicide manufacturing, Herbicide transportation, Herbicide application	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Herbicides – organic (O)				
	Pesticides – chemical (O)	Pesticide manufacturing, Pesticide transport, Pesticide application			
Pesticides – organic (O)					
Soil quality	Organic matter content of soil (O, N)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/m3
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Surface runoff - not captured by stormwater sewers (O, N, C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m3/d, m3/yr
Water quality	Infiltration to groundwater (O, N, C)	Recharge of water into groundwater resources	✓	✓	m3/yr, in/h, mL/h
Water scarcity	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O, N, C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓	✓	m3/yr

Table S20. System boundary infosheet for unsealed car parks

Name of the NBS		Unsealed car parks	
NBS Typology		Structures associated to urban networks	
Description		Unsealed parking lots are characterized by permeable surfaces for stormwater management. They can be used for low-traffic roads, parking lots, driveways or walkways.	
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ More infiltration surface, ○ Less flood risks, ○ Groundwater replenishment, ○ Reduced runoff water volume, ○ Increased water infiltration, ○ Reduced flood effect, ○ Substrate/drainage can be recycled ○ Increased soil surface, ○ Habitat for organisms ○ Decrease in irrigation needs due to water reclamation (link between water and energy) ○ Changes in water stocks (temporal flows) at larger scales (e.g. groundwater sources recharge) ○ Reduction in urban heat island effect because of the cooling effect of evapotranspiration 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Pollutants and emissions from vehicles ○ Grey infrastructure construction materials required ○ Emissions from construction vehicles
Neighbourhood scale	Impacts are low when compared to object scale but the abovementioned impacts can occur at this scale too.		
City scale			

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Avoided GHG emissions	GHG emissions released (O, N)	All GHG emitting processes including combustion, Energy generation, Transportation, Biogenic and anthropogenic	✓		kg CO2 eq/yr, kg CO2 eq/kg of product
Common air quality index	Air pollutants released from vehicles (O, N)	Transportation activities, Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation	✓	✓	ug/m3, mg/m3, mg/m3/d, ug/m3/d, kg/m3/yr
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for water supply (O, N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for water treatment (O, N)				
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for water supply (O, N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for water treatment (O, N)				

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Raw material efficiency	Construction materials avoided (O)	Manufacturing of construction materials, Transportation construction materials	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Soil quality	Organic matter content of soil (O, N)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/m ³
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Infiltration to groundwater (O, N)	Recharge of water into groundwater resources	✓	✓	m ³ /yr, in/h, mL/h
	Surface runoff - not captured by stormwater sewers (O, N)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Water quality	Infiltration to groundwater (O, N)	Recharge of water into groundwater resources	✓	✓	m ³ /yr, in/h, mL/h
Water scarcity	Stormwater into sewer (O, N)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		m ³ /yr
	Water supply from alternative sources than supply system (O, N)	Pumping, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr

Table S21. System boundary infosheet for meadow

Name of the NBS		Meadow	
NBS Typology		Structures characterized by food and resources production	
Description			
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks ○ Capture atmospheric CO2 during natural lighting hours ○ Flood control ○ Water management ○ Water holding capacity ○ Water remediation ○ Changes in local water stocks (temporal flows) ○ Composting ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration ○ Increased soil quality ○ Soil organisms ○ Biodiversity ○ Aesthetics 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Fertilizer ○ Herbicides ○ Insecticides ○ Pesticides usage ○ Energy demand for maintenance ○ Water demand for irrigation
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks ○ Capture atmospheric CO2 during natural lighting hours ○ Flood control ○ Water management ○ Reduction in urban heat island effect because of the cooling effect of evapotranspiration ○ Increased green areas ○ Enhanced water retention capacity ○ Reduced runoff and improved flood regulation (link between water and energy) ○ Decrease of feed miles due to local feed production ○ Changes in water stocks (temporal flows) at larger scales (e.g. groundwater sources recharge) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Energy demand for maintenance ○ Water demand for irrigation
City scale			N/A

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO ₂ sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O, N)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO ₂ eq/10 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq/100 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq per amount of biomass
Avoided GHG emissions	GHG emissions avoided (O, N)	All GHG emitting processes including combustion, Energy generation, Transportation	✓	✓	kg CO ₂ eq/yr, kg CO ₂ eq/kg of product
Common air quality index	Air pollutants removed (O, N)	Direct capture by leaves, NO _x and PM capture	✓		µg/ m ³ , mg/ m ³ , kg/yr
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for maintenance (O, N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for maintenance (O, N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Raw material efficiency	Fertilizers-chemical (O)	Fertilizer manufacturing, Fertilizer transport, Fertilizer spreading	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Fertilizers-organic (O)	Fertilizer manufacturing, Fertilizer transport, Fertilizer spreading	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Food supply – of plant origin (O, N)	Urban agriculture, Transportation of produce, Fuel consumption, Irrigation processes, Production and transportation of agricultural chemicals, Consumption of resources for maintenance, Conventional farming activities	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Fuel consumption for vehicles (O, N)	Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation, Fuel combustion	✓		L/100 km, L/km, m ³ /yr, MJ/yr, kg/d, kg/yr
	Herbicides-chemical (O)	Herbicide manufacturing, Herbicide transportation, Herbicide application	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Herbicides-organic (O)	Herbicide manufacturing, Herbicide transportation, Herbicide application	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Insecticides-chemical (O)	Insecticide manufacturing, Insecticide transport, Insecticide application	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Insecticides-organic (O)	Insecticide manufacturing, Insecticide transport, Insecticide application	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Pesticides-chemical (O)	Pesticide manufacturing, Pesticide transport, Pesticide application	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Pesticides-organic (O)	Pesticide manufacturing, Pesticide transport, Pesticide application	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Water demand for irrigation (O, N)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Soil quality	Nutrients to soil (O, N)	Agricultural processes, Urban farming processes, Manufacturing industry, NBS maintenance	✓	✓	kg/ha, g nutrient/kg soil, mg/L
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O, N)	Wastewater treatment, manufacturing of chemicals, transportation of chemicals	✓		m ³ /yr
	Surface runoff – not captured by stormwater sewers (O, N)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Water quality	Infiltration to groundwater (O, N)	Recharge of water into groundwater resources	✓	✓	m ³ /yr, in/h, mL/h
Water scarcity	Water demand for irrigation (O, N)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr

Table S22. System boundary infosheet for urban farms

Name of the NBS		Urban farms	
NBS Typology		Structures characterized by food and resources production	
Description			
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Fertile grounds, food production at local scale ○ Varied plant species, but mainly artificially planted ○ Increased soil quality, soil organisms ○ Efficient utilization of rain water ○ Water holding capacity, water remediation ○ Biodiversity ○ Aesthetics ○ Avoidance of transported food (fuel savings, carbon savings) ○ Composting ○ Delocalization of the waste generation ○ Lower generation of waste ○ Increased efficiency in the use of energy and materials 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Water demand ○ Energy demand ○ Herbicide requirement ○ Waste generation
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Food production at local scale ○ Biodiversity ○ Aesthetics ○ Avoidance of transported food (fuel savings, carbon savings) ○ Composting 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Water demand ○ Energy demand
City scale	Impact at this scale is less relevant		

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO ₂ sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O, N)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO ₂ eq/10 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq/100 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq per amount of biomass
Avoided GHG emissions	GHG emissions avoided (O, N)	All GHG emitting processes including combustion	✓	✓	kg CO ₂ eq/yr, kg CO ₂ eq/kg of product
Common air quality index	Air pollutants avoided (O, N)	Emissions avoided (by reducing current practices and operations), Best management practices	✓	✓	µg/ m ³ , mg/ m ³ , kg/yr
Cumulative energy demands	Fuel consumption avoided (O, N)	Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation, Fuel combustion	✓		L/100 km, L/km, m ³ /yr, MJ/yr, kg/d, kg/yr

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for water supply (O, N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Material circularity indicator	Waste recycled (O)	Recycling processes, Incineration process, Composting, Energy generation, Water pumping and treatment	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Per capita food production variability	Food supply – of plant origin (O, N)	Urban agriculture, Transportation of produce, Fuel consumption, Irrigation processes, Production and transportation of agricultural chemicals, Consumption of resources for maintenance, Conventional farming activities	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Raw material efficiency	Compost (O)	Composting, Energy generation, Fuel consumption, Water consumption, Transportation	✓		kg/yr, t/yr
	Food supply – of plant origin (O, N)	Urban agriculture, Transportation of produce, Fuel consumption, Irrigation processes, Production and transportation of agricultural chemicals, Consumption of resources for maintenance, Conventional farming activities	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Fuel consumption avoided (O, N)	Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation, Fuel combustion	✓		L/100 km, L/km, m ³ /yr, MJ/yr, kg/d, kg/yr
	Herbicides-chemical (O)	Herbicide manufacturing, Herbicide transportation, Herbicide application	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Other resource (O, N, C)	All relevant processes producing or consuming resources not specified elsewhere in the list	✓	✓	kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Water demand for irrigation (O, N)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary			L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Soil quality	Organic matter content of soil (O)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/m ³
Specific waste generation	Waste generated (O)	All waste generating processes	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Stormwater avoided into sewer (O, N)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		m ³ /yr
	Surface runoff – not captured by stormwater sewers (O, N)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Water scarcity	Water demand for irrigation (O, N)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
	Water supply from alternative sources than supply system (O)	Pumping, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr

Table S23. System boundary infosheet for urban forests

Name of the NBS		Urban forests	
NBS Typology		Structures characterized by food and resources production	
Description		Urban forest is defined as all publicly and privately owned trees within an urban area. This term includes individual trees along streets and in backyards, as well as stands of remnant forest (Nowak et al. 2010). Urban forests are an integral part of urban ecosystems, which includes different elements (people, animals, buildings, infrastructure, water and air) that interact to significantly affect the quality of urban life. The definition of “urban land” must be included into the urban forest definition. The term “urban” connotes areas with relatively high amounts of people and artificial surfaces. And the term “urban land” will be used to define the different kinds of urban forest, depending on the scale and location (Nowak, 2010).	
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks, ○ Capture of atmospheric CO2 during natural lighting hours, ○ Reduce common air quality index background levels (Red_CAI_BGL); ○ Better air quality inside (Bet_AQ_in) - Mainly in Particle matter (PM) and less in NOx, ○ More infiltration surface, ○ Less runoff risks, ○ Groundwater replenishment, ○ Flood protection, ○ Water holding capacity ○ Water remediation ○ Increase in water resources due to water reclamation, ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration, ○ Certain tree species can reduce water supply due to evapotranspiration (benefit in regions prone to flooding but problem in arid or semi-arid regions), ○ Biodiversity, ○ Increased soil surface, ○ Soil organisms, ○ Aesthetics, ○ Reduction in urban heat island effect, ○ Positive impact on energy consumption of surrounding buildings due to cooling effect, ○ Indirect impact on energy efficiency of surrounding buildings in the neighbourhood. 	<p>Increase in transportation demand should be considered as a result of recreational effect on the population (may lead to an increase in fossil fuel/primary energy consumption from the visitor vehicles)</p>	
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ CO2 sequestration, ○ Reduced cooling energy demands of neighbourhood buildings, ○ Water reclamation, ○ Air pollutant filtration at larger scales 		
City scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ CO2 sequestration, ○ Air pollutant filtration, ○ Water reclamation 		

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO2 sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O, N, C)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO2 eq/10 yrs, kg CO2 eq/100 yrs, kg CO2 eq per amount of biomass
Avoided GHG emissions	GHG emissions released (O, N, C)	All GHG emitting processes including combustion, Energy generation, Transportation, Biogenic and anthropogenic	✓		kg CO2 eq/yr, kg CO2 eq/kg of product
Building energy needs	Energy demand for cooling (N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Common air quality index	Air pollutants released from vehicles (O, N, C)	Transportation activities, Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation	✓	✓	ug/m3, mg/m3, mg/m3/d, ug/m3/d, kg/m3/yr
	Air pollutants removed (O, N, C)	Direct capture by leaves, NOx and PM capture	✓	✓	µg/m3, mg/m3, kg/year
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for cooling (N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for cooling (N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for water supply (O, N, C)				
	Energy demand for water treatment (O, N, C)				
Raw material efficiency	Chemicals used for water treatment (O)	Water treatment, Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing processes for chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		g/d, kg/d, kg/yr, ton/yr
	Fuel consumption for vehicles (O)	Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation, Fuel combustion	✓		L/100 km, L/km, m3/yr, MJ/yr, kg/d, kg/yr
	Herbicides – chemical (O)	Herbicide manufacturing, Herbicide transportation, Herbicide application	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Herbicides – organic (O)				
	Pesticides – chemical (O)	Pesticide manufacturing, Pesticide transport, Pesticide application	✓		
Pesticides – organic (O)					

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Soil quality	Organic matter content of soil (O, N)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/m ³
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Surface runoff - not captured by stormwater sewers (O, N, C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Water quality	Infiltration to groundwater (O, N, C)	Recharge of water into groundwater resources	✓	✓	m ³ /yr, in/h, mL/h
Water scarcity	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O, N, C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓	✓	m ³ /yr

Table S24. System boundary infosheet for urban orchards

Name of the NBS		Urban orchards	
NBS Typology		Structures characterized by food and resources production	
Description		It is an area of land devoted to cultivation, preferable in an organic way, of vegetables or fruits and flowers. These organic surfaces are located in the urban area. In general, non-profit associations, neighbourhood associations or the city council usually manage them. Unemployed, retired people, families with limited resources or people interested in it usually may exploit them. It is a social space where people and families profit of nature and healthy vegetables from orchards.	
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks ○ Capture atmospheric CO2 during natural lighting hours ○ Flood protection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration ○ Reduce water supply due to evapotranspiration (benefit in regions prone to flooding but problem in arid or semi-arid regions) ○ Biodiversity ○ Food production ○ Increased soil quality, soil organisms, water holding capacity, water remediation ○ Aesthetics ○ Reduction in urban heat island effect because of the cooling effect of evapotranspiration ○ Increased green areas ○ Enhanced water retention capacity ○ Reduced runoff and improved flood regulation (link between water and energy) ○ Avoidance of transported food (fuel savings, carbon savings) ○ Create an isolation effect impacting heating and cooling demands of buildings if implemented on rooftops, changes in local water stocks (temporal flows) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Any increase in water consumption ○ Energy demands
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration ○ Reduce water supply due to evapotranspiration (benefit in regions prone to flooding but problem in arid or semi-arid regions) ○ Biodiversity ○ Food production ○ Increased soil quality, soil organisms, water holding capacity, water remediation ○ Aesthetics ○ Reduction in urban heat island effect because of the cooling effect of evapotranspiration ○ Increased green areas ○ Enhanced water retention capacity ○ Reduced runoff and improved flood regulation (link between water and energy) ○ Avoidance of transported food (fuel savings, carbon savings) ○ Create an isolation effect impacting heating and cooling demands of buildings if implemented on rooftops, changes in local water stocks (temporal flows) 		
City scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Create an isolation effect impacting heating and cooling demands of buildings if implemented on rooftops ○ Reduction in urban heat island effect because of the cooling effect of evapotranspiration 	N/A	

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO ₂ sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O, N)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO ₂ eq/10 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq/100 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq per amount of biomass
Building energy needs	Energy demand for cooling (O, N, C)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for heating (O, N, C)				
Common air quality index	Air pollutants avoided (O, N, C)	Emissions avoided (by reducing current practices and operations), Best management practices	✓	✓	µg/ m ³ , mg/ m ³ , kg/yr

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for cooling (O, N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for cooling (O, N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for maintenance (O, N)				
	Energy demand for water supply (O, N)				
Per capita food production variability	Food supply – of plant origin (O, N, C)	Urban agriculture, Transportation of produce, Fuel consumption, Irrigation processes, Production and transportation of agricultural chemicals, Consumption of resources for maintenance, Conventional farming activities	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Raw material efficiency	Food supply – of plant origin (O, N, C)	Urban agriculture, Transportation of produce, Fuel consumption, Irrigation processes, Production and transportation of agricultural chemicals, Consumption of resources for maintenance, Conventional farming activities	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Fuel consumption for vehicles (O, N, C)	Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation, Fuel combustion	✓		L/100 km, L/km, m ³ /yr, MJ/yr
	Water demand for irrigation (O, N)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Soil quality	Organic matter content of soil (O, N)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/m ³
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O, N)	Wastewater treatment, manufacturing of chemicals, transportation of chemicals	✓		m ³ /yr
	Surface runoff – not captured by stormwater sewers (O, N)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Water scarcity	Water demand for irrigation (O, N)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr

Table S25. System boundary infosheet for urban vineyard

Name of the NBS		Urban vineyard	
NBS Typology		Structures characterized by food and resources production	
Description	This is an urban area where grapes are grown for market sales and for wine making. First, it plays a metaphoric role in the urban green spaces – it brings back the historicity of the landscape, provides space for activity of people near the nature, thus this NBS entity has great social and mental relevance. The capacity of the vineyard in the carbon - sink should be mentioned too. The vineyards could represent a crucial cropping system able to provide pivotal ecological services such as carbon dioxide sequestration. Viticulture can also contribute to the preservation and regulation of natural resources, such as soil and agricultural landscapes.		
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks ○ Capture atmospheric CO₂ during natural lighting hours ○ Flood protection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration ○ Certain tree species can reduce water supply due to evapotranspiration (benefit in regions prone to flooding but problem in arid or semi-arid regions) ○ Biodiversity ○ Fertile grounds ○ Food production ○ Increased soil quality, soil organisms, water holding capacity, water remediation ○ Aesthetics ○ Avoidance of transported food (fuel savings, carbon savings) ○ Create an isolation effect impacting heating and cooling demands of buildings if implemented on rooftops , Increased efficiency in the use of energy and materials ○ Design with nature can create new dynamic spaces that increase property values, thus attracting investors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Possible increased water utilization in summer times
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 		
City scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 		

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO ₂ sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O, N,C)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO ₂ eq/10 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq/100 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq per amount of biomass
Building energy needs	Energy demand for cooling (O, N, C)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for heating (O, N, C)				
Common air quality index	Air pollutants avoided (O, N, C)	Emissions avoided (by reducing current practices and operations), Best management practices	✓	✓	µg/ m ³ , mg/ m ³ , kg/yr
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for cooling (O, N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for cooling (O, N)				

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
	Energy demand for maintenance (O, N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for water supply (O, N)				
Per capita food production variability	Food supply – of plant origin (C)	Urban agriculture, Transportation of produce, Fuel consumption, Irrigation processes, Production and transportation of agricultural chemicals, Consumption of resources for maintenance, Conventional farming activities	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Raw material efficiency	Fertilizer chemical (N, C)	Fertilizer manufacturing, Fertilizer transport, Fertilizer spreading	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Fertilizer organic (N, C)	Fertilizer manufacturing, Fertilizer transport, Fertilizer spreading	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Food supply – of plant origin (N, C)	Urban agriculture, Transportation of produce, Fuel consumption, Irrigation processes, Production and transportation of agricultural chemicals, Consumption of resources for maintenance, Conventional farming activities	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Fuel consumption for vehicles (N, C)	Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation, Fuel combustion	✓		L/100 km, L/km, m ³ /yr, MJ/yr
	Pesticides chemical (N, C)	Pesticide manufacturing, Pesticide transport, Pesticide application	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Pesticides organic (N, C)	Pesticide manufacturing, Pesticide transport, Pesticide application	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Water demand for irrigation (N, C)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Soil quality	Organic matter content of soil (O, N, C)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/m ³
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O, N)	Wastewater treatment, manufacturing of chemicals, transportation of chemicals	✓		m ³ /yr
	Surface runoff – not captured by stormwater sewers (O, N)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Water scarcity	Water demand for irrigation (O, N)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr

Table S26. System boundary infosheet for vegeTable Sgardens

Name of the NBS		VegeTable Sgardens	
NBS Typology		Structures characterized by food and resources production	
Description		This NBS is an area of land dedicated to the cultivation of vegetables, fruits and flowers, for the purpose of food production. This kind of solutions takes place in public spaces, community gardens or private residential property. Unemployed, retired people, families with limited resource or people interested in it are usually in charge of exploiting them.	
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Fertile grounds, ○ Food production at local scale, ○ Varied plant species, but mainly artificially planted, ○ Increased soil quality, ○ Soil organisms, ○ Efficient utilization of rain water, ○ Water holding capacity, ○ Water remediation, ○ Biodiversity, ○ Aesthetics, ○ Avoidance of transported food (fuel savings, carbon savings), ○ Composting ○ Energy efficiency: May create an isolation effect impacting heating and cooling demands of buildings if implemented on rooftops ○ Low reduced common air quality index background levels (low Red_CAI_BGL) 		Any increase in water consumption should be investigated.
Neighbourhood scale	<p>Impact at this scale is limited and depends on the covered area.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Food production at local scale, ○ Biodiversity, ○ Aesthetics, ○ Avoidance of transported food (fuel savings, carbon savings) 		
City scale	N/A		N/A

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO2 sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O, N)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO2 eq/10 yrs, kg CO2 eq/100 yrs, kg CO2 eq per amount of biomass

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Avoided GHG emissions	GHG emissions avoided (O, N)	All GHG emitting processes including combustion, Energy generation, Transportation	✓	✓	kg CO2 eq/yr, kg CO2 eq/kg of product
Common air quality index	Air pollutants avoided (O, N)	Emissions avoided (by reducing current practices or operations), Best management practices	✓	✓	µg/m3, mg/m3, kg/year
	Air pollutants released from vehicles (O, N)	Transportation activities, Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation	✓		mg/m3, µg/m3, mg/m3/d, µg/m3/d, kg/m3/yr
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for maintenance (O, N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy generated by renewable resources (O, N)				
Per capita food production variability	Food supply – of plant origin (O, N)	Urban agriculture, Transportation of produce, Fuel consumption, Irrigation processes, Production and transportation of agricultural chemicals, Consumption of resources for maintenance, Conventional farming activities	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Raw material efficiency	Compost (O)	Composting, Energy generation, Fuel consumption, Water consumption, Transportation	✓		kg/yr, t/yr
	Food supply – of plant origin (O, N)	Urban agriculture, Transportation of produce, Fuel consumption, Irrigation processes, Production and transportation of agricultural chemicals, Consumption of resources for maintenance, Conventional farming activities	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Fuel consumption avoided(O)	Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation, Fuel combustion	✓	✓	L/100 km, L/km, m3/yr, MJ/yr, kg/d, kg/yr
	Herbicides – chemical (O)	Herbicide manufacturing, Herbicide transportation, Herbicide application	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Water demand for irrigation (O, N)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m3/d, m3/yr
	Water for maintenance (O, N)	Pumping operations, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m3/d, m3/yr
Soil quality	Organic matter content of soil (O)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/m ³
Water scarcity	Water demand for irrigation (O, N)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m3/d, m3/yr
	Water for maintenance (O, N)	Pumping operations, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m3/d, m3/yr

Table S27. System boundary infosheet for phytoremediation-management of polluted areas by plants

Name of the NBS		Phytoremediation Management of polluted areas by plants	
NBS Typology		Ecological restoration	
Description	This NBS is based on the use of plants and trees and their interactions with microorganisms for the treatment of polluted soils. The concept is very broad and therefore covers a range of relatively different technologies. We should talk about phytoremediations.		
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Sustainable land use ○ Rebuilt soil structure with plant roots ○ Soil improvement by contamination treatment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Fertilizer use may be needed 	
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Soil erosion control ○ Soil fertility ○ Extraction of valuable metals (phytomining) ○ Indirectly related with water reclamation and rainwater infiltration, aesthetics, biodiversity 		
City scale	Impact at this scale is limited		N/A

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for water supply (O, N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for water treatment (O, N)				
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for soil treatment (O, N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for water supply (O, N)				
	Energy demand for water treatment (O, N)				
Raw material efficiency	Fertilizers-chemical (O, N)	Fertilizer manufacturing, Fertilizer transport, Fertilizer spreading	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Fertilizers-organic (O, N)				
	Metals extracted from soil (O, N)	Extraction/recycling processes by plants, Conventional bioremediation technologies	✓		kg/yr, t/yr
	Water demand for irrigation (O, N)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Soil contamination	Soil pollutants removed (O, N)	Soil remediation, Phytoremediation, Bioremediation	✓		kg/ m ³ , kg/ m ³ /yr
Soil quality	Organic matter content of soil (O, N)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/m ³
	Toxic pollutants into soil (O, N)	All toxic pollutant generating processes	✓	✓	g PTE/yr, mg/m ³ , ug/ m ³ , ng/ m ³ , mg/yr
Water quality	Toxic pollutants into water (O, N)	All toxic pollutant generating processes	✓	✓	mg/ m ³ , ug/ m ³ , ng/ m ³ , mg/yr
	Water pollutants removed (O, N)	Water treatment, Phytoremediation, Energy generation, Chemical manufacturing and transport, Disposal activities for treatment residues	✓		mg/L, ug/L, kg/ m ³ , kg/L, kg/yr

Table S28. System boundary infosheet for quarry restoration

Name of the NBS		Quarry restoration	
NBS Typology		Ecological restoration	
Description			
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Impacts are very variable and dependent on the target of restoration (agricultural use, recreational use etc.). ○ Top 3 habitats: wetlands, heathland, grasslands) ○ Renewable energy (from landfill, geothermal), ○ Biodiversity, ○ Crop production, ○ Flood control by water storage, ○ Carbon sequestration, ○ Air pollutant removed, ○ Water regulation, ○ Reduced erosion, ○ Reduced nutrient run-off, ○ Soil organic matter increase fresh water, food production ○ Waste detoxification by plant-soil systems (water quality) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Peat extraction (fuel and horticultural use) ○ Construction materials, ○ Emissions from construction vehicles and/or visitor vehicles
Neighbourhood scale			N/A
City scale			N/A

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO2 sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO2 eq/10 yrs, kg CO2 eq/100 yrs, kg CO2 eq per amount of biomass
Avoided GHG emissions	GHG emissions released (O)	All GHG emitting processes including combustion, Energy generation, Transportation, Biogenic and anthropogenic	✓		kg CO2 eq/yr, kg CO2 eq/kg of product
Common air quality index	Air pollutants released from vehicles (O)	Transportation activities, Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation		✓	mg/m3, ug/m3, mg/m3/d, ug/m3/d, kg/m3/yr
Energy efficiency Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for construction (O)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for maintenance (O)				
	Energy demand for water treatment (O)				
	Energy generated by renewable resources (O)	Energy generation, Solar power generation, Wind power generation, Hydropower generation, Geothermal power generation			

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Material circularity indicator	Food supply – of plant origin (O)	Urban agriculture, Transportation of produce, Fuel consumption, Irrigation processes, Production and transportation of agricultural chemicals, Consumption of resources for maintenance, Conventional farming activities	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Raw material efficiency	Chemicals used for water treatment (O)	Water treatment, Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing processes for chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		g/d, kg/d, kg/yr, ton/yr
	Construction materials required (O)	Manufacturing of construction materials, Transportation construction materials	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Food supply – of plant origin (O)	Urban agriculture, Transportation of produce, Fuel consumption, Irrigation processes, Production and transportation of agricultural chemicals, Consumption of resources for maintenance, Conventional farming activities	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Fuel consumption for vehicles (O)	Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation, Fuel combustion	✓		L/100 km, L/km, m3/yr, MJ/yr, kg/d, kg/yr
Soil quality	Organic matter content of soil (O)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/m3
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		m3/yr
	Surface runoff - not captured by stormwater sewers (O)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m3/d, m3/yr
Water quality	Eroded soil into waterbodies (O)	Erosion process		✓	kg/yr, t/yr, m3/yr
	Water pollutants removed (O)	Water treatment, Phytoremediation, Energy production, Chemical manufacturing and transport, Disposal activities for treatment residues	✓		mg/L, ug/L, kg/m3, kg/L, kg/yr
Water scarcity	Infiltration to groundwater (O)	Recharge of water into groundwater resources	✓	✓	m3/yr, in/h, mL/h
	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		m3/yr
	Water supply from alternative sources than supply system	Pumping, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m3/d, m3/yr

Table S29. System boundary infosheet for rustic plants-horticultural but non-invasive plants-indigenous species-diversity of plant species-plants with bio-filter features

Name of the NBS		Rustic plants Horticultural but non-invasive plants Indigenous species Non-allergic species Diversity of plant species Plants with bio-filter features	
NBS Typology		Choice of plants	
Description			
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<p>There may not be specific measurable impact but impacts linked with vegetation can also be related to these NBS.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Flood protection, ○ Sustainable land use, ○ Rebuilt soil structure with plant roots, ○ Soil improvement by contamination treatment, ○ Aesthetics, ○ Biodiversity, ○ Indirect water reclamation potential dependent on the selected plant characteristics, ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration, ○ Certain species can reduce water supply due to evapotranspiration (benefit in regions prone to flooding but problem in arid or semi-arid regions), ○ Reduced common air quality index background levels ○ Carbon sequestration 		
Neighbourhood scale			
City scale			

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO2 sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O, N, C)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO2 eq/10 yrs, kg CO2 eq/100 yrs, kg CO2 eq per amount of biomass
Common air quality index	Air pollutants removed (O, N, C)	Direct capture by leaves, NOx and PM capture		✓	µg/m3, mg/m3, k g/year

On the Ground

Table S30. System boundary infosheet for vegetation systems for slope erosion control/vegetation engineering systems for wind erosion control

Name of the NBS		Vegetation systems for slope erosion control Vegetation engineering systems for wind erosion control	
NBS Typology		Systems for erosion control	
Description	Stabilizing soils structure on steepened slopes through revegetation in order to minimize or prevent the erosion of soil by wind or rain and landslides, avoiding sedimentation problems. When the slope is really steeped, the most common slope stabilization and erosion prevention method is some kind of retaining slopes method joined with revegetation. In order to stabilize steepened slopes, some kind of soil retention method is nevertheless needed; joining it with a well-established vegetative cover is one of the most effective methods of reducing erosion in unsTable S slopes steeper than 2H:1V. The retention method keeps the soil meanwhile vegetation protects soil surfaces from rain generated splash erosion and can help to slow runoff flows across a disturbed ground. In addition, plant roots hold their soil in place, keeping it from washing away during rainstorms. Lastly, trees help to prevent high winds from blowing away top soil because the trees provide windbreaks, which can prevent high winds.		
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Flood and erosion protection ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration ○ Biodiversity ○ Reduced slope erosion risks in addition to above-mentioned impacts 		
Neighbourhood scale			
City scale			

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Cumulative energy demands	Energy consumption avoided (C)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources		✓	J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for construction (C)		✓		
Raw material efficiency	Infiltration to groundwater (O, N, C)	Recharge of water into groundwater resources	✓		m ³ /yr, in/h, mL/h
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O, N, C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		m ³ /yr
	Surface runoff - not captured by stormwater sewers (O, N, C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Water quality	Eroded soil into waterbodies (O)	Erosion process		✓	kg/yr, t/yr, m ³ /yr

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Water scarcity	Infiltration to groundwater (O, N, C)	Recharge of water into groundwater resources	✓		m ³ /yr, in/h, mL/h

Table S31. System boundary infosheet for mulching

Name of the NBS		Mulching	
NBS Typology		Works on soil	
Description	Mulching is a technique used in plantations and maintenance that consists in covering the surface of the soil with an organic, mineral or plastic material in a continuous (film) or discontinuous way (grains, fragments, etc.) to protect the ground and plants mainly against weeds and soil evaporation. Originally, the term was created in 1935 to designate the action of mulching the soil (Loreau, 2014). In addition, mulching is one promising technology that is an integral component of conservation farming and is increasingly seen in the light of integrated soil management—an essential building stone for sustainable agriculture. The use of mulch has great agro-ecological potential—it typically conserves the soil, improves the soil ecology, stabilizes and enhances crop yield and provides various environmental services (Erenstein, 2003).		
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Flood and erosion protection ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration ○ Biodiversity ○ Soil carbon storage ○ Increased soil quality ○ Biodiversity ○ Waste management (if waste is used for amelioration) ○ Potential for increased food production ○ Increased filter capacity ○ Habitat for soil organisms ○ Soil fertility ○ Water holding capacity ○ Mulching soil can help keep it moist in between rain or irrigation ○ Carbon sequestration ○ Higher food production potential with the improved soil quality ○ Increased nutrients in the soil ○ Water reclamation ○ Reduction in water demand from supply system ○ Reduced load from run-off into sewerage systems 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Increase in surface runoff for impermeable mulches ○ Increase unwanted chemicals in soil
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Carbon sequestration ○ Higher food production potential with the improved soil quality ○ Increased nutrients in the soil 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Energy demand for cutting of wood ○ Fuel consumption during transportation ○ Air pollutants released
City scale	N/A		N/A

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Avoided GHG emissions	GHG emissions released (O)	All GHG emitting processes including combustion, Energy generation, Transportation, Biogenic and anthropogenic	✓		kg CO ₂ eq/yr, kg CO ₂ eq/kg of product
Common air quality index	Air pollutants released from vehicles (O)	Transportation activities, Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation	✓		mg/ m ³ , ug/ m ³ , mg/ m ³ /d, ug/ m ³ /d, kg/ m ³ /yr
Efficiency of valorisation as a result of recycling process	Waste recycled (O, N, C)	Recycling processes, Incineration process, Composting, Energy generation, Water pumping and treatment	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Material circularity indicator	Waste recycled (O)	Recycling processes, Incineration process, Composting, Energy generation, Water pumping and treatment	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Raw material efficiency	Food supply – of plant origin (O, N)	Urban agriculture, Transportation of produce, Fuel consumption, Irrigation processes, Production and transportation of agricultural chemicals, Consumption of resources for maintenance, Conventional farming activities	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Fuel consumption for vehicles (N)	Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation, Fuel combustion	✓		L/100 km, L/km, m ³ /yr, MJ/yr
	Other resource (O, N)	All relevant processes producing or consuming resources not specified elsewhere in the list	✓	✓	kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Soil quality	Chemicals avoided (O)	Manufacturing processes for chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, Treatment processes for medium contaminated with chemicals		✓	g/d, kg/d, kg/yr, ton/yr
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Stormwater avoided into the sewer	Wastewater treatment, manufacturing of chemicals, transportation of chemicals	✓		m ³ /yr
	Surface runoff – not captured by stormwater sewers	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
	Surface runoff – not captured by stormwater sewers	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr

Table S32. System boundary infosheet for soil amelioration/amendment/improvement -smart soils- reinforced/structural soil

Name of the NBS		Soil amelioration/amendment/improvement Smart soils Reinforced/structural soil	
NBS Typology		Works on soil	
Description	The soil improvement or fertility is not limited to its consistency as a medium of culture and its mineral content, but to a set of agricultural practices dependent on the environment and the choices of the farmer. To maintain the performance of this environment, which seems to be the main source of food production, it is essential to supply all the physical, biological and chemical constituents (Huber and Schaub, 2011). Increasing soil agronomic quality is also another way of soil improvement. This includes: (i) integrating or improving nutrient management, (ii) increasing carbon sequestration, (iii) enhancing water infiltration, (iv) ensuring water at the plant-root zone and (v) encouraging beneficial soil organisms (Council et al., 2009).		
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Flood and erosion protection ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration ○ Biodiversity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Soil carbon storage ○ Increased soil quality ○ Waste management (if waste is used for amelioration) ○ Potential for increased food production ○ Increased filter capacity ○ Habitat for soil organisms ○ Soil fertility ○ Water holding capacity ○ Carbon sequestration ○ Higher food production potential with the improved soil quality increased nutrients in the soil 	N/A
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Increased soil quality ○ Waste management (if waste is used for amelioration) ○ Potential for increased food production ○ Increased filter capacity ○ Habitat for soil organisms ○ Soil fertility ○ Water holding capacity ○ Carbon sequestration ○ Higher food production potential with the improved soil quality increased nutrients in the soil 		
City scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Flood and erosion protection ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration ○ Biodiversity ○ Carbon sequestration ○ Higher food production potential with the improved soil quality ○ Increased nutrients in the soil 		

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Common air quality index	Air pollutants removed (O)	Direct capture by leaves, NOx and PM capture	✓		µg/ m ³ , mg/ m ³ , kg/year

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Efficiency of valorisation as a result of recycling process	Waste recycled (O)	Recycling processes, Incineration process, Composting, Energy generation, Water pumping and treatment	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for water supply (O, N, C)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Raw material efficiency	Food supply – of plant origin (O, N, C)	Urban agriculture, Transportation of produce, Fuel consumption, Irrigation processes, Production and transportation of agricultural chemicals, Consumption of resources for maintenance, Conventional farming activities	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Other resource (O, N, C)	All relevant processes producing or consuming resources not specified elsewhere in the list		✓	kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Soil quality	Soil pollutants removed (O, N)	Soil remediation, Phytoremediation, Bioremediation	✓		kg/ m ³ , kg/ m ³ /yr
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Surface runoff not captured by stormwater sewers (O, N, C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr

Water

Table S33. System boundary infosheet for excavation of new water bodies-infrastructure removed on rivers

Name of the NBS		Excavation of new water bodies Infrastructure removed on rivers	
NBS Typology		Natural and semi-natural water bodies and hydrographic network	
Description			
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Reduced Run-off, ○ Flood peak reductions/Increase in time to peak, ○ Reduced load from run-off into sewerage systems, ○ Increased infiltration/water storage, ○ Enhanced water retention capacity in the area, ○ Water reclamation potential, ○ Reduced damages from drought, ○ Increased evapotranspiration, ○ Reduced urban heat island effect, ○ Improved water quality/reduced pollutants, ○ Biodiversity, ○ Rebuilt soil structure with water, ○ Soil improvement potential 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Potential of fuel usage and emissions from the machines at the reconstruction phase
Neighbourhood scale			
City scale	N/A		N/A

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO2 sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O, N)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO2 eq/10 yrs, kg CO2 eq/100 yrs, kg CO2 eq per amount of biomass
Avoided GHG emissions	GHG emissions released (O, N)	All GHG emitting processes including combustion, Energy generation, Transportation, Biogenic and anthropogenic	✓		kg CO2 eq/yr, kg CO2 eq/kg of product
Common air quality index	Air pollutants released from vehicles (O, N)	Transportation activities, Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation	✓	✓	mg/m3, ug/m3, mg/m3/d, ug/m3/d, kg/m3/yr
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for water supply (O, N)		✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, Kwh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for water treatment (O, N)				

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for water supply (O, N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources			
	Energy demand for water treatment (O, N)				
Peak flow variation	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O, N)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		m3/yr
Raw material efficiency	Chemicals used for water treatment (O, N)	Water treatment, Wastewater treatment, manufacturing processes for chemicals, transportation of chemicals	✓		g/d, kg/d, kg/yr, ton/yr
	Construction materials required (O, N)	Manufacturing of construction materials, Transportation construction materials	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Fuel consumption for vehicles (O, N)	Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation, Fuel combustion	✓		L/100 km, L/km, m3/yr, MJ/yr
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Surface runoff - not captured by stormwater sewers (O, N)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m3/d, m3/yr
Water quality	Infiltration to groundwater (O, N)	Recharge of water into groundwater resources	✓	✓	m3/yr, in/h, mL/h
Water scarcity	Water demand from supply system - for human consumption (O, N)	Water treatment, Pumping operation for water supply, Manufacturing and transportation of treatment chemicals, Energy generation, Disposal activities for treatment residues	✓		L/hr, L/d, m3/d, m3/yr

Table S34. System boundary infosheet for gravity fountain

Name of the NBS		Gravity fountain	
NBS Typology		Natural and semi-natural water bodies and hydrographic network	
Description			
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Aesthetics, ○ Enhanced water retention capacity in the area, ○ Increased evapotranspiration, ○ Very low impact on CAI (common air quality index) 		
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Reduced damages from drought, ○ Reduced urban heat island effect 		
City scale	Very low impact		

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for cooling (O, N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Surface runoff - not captured by stormwater sewers (O, N)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Water scarcity	Water demand for irrigation (O, N)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
	Water supply from alternative sources than supply system (O, N)	Pumping, Water treatment if necessary			

Table S35. System boundary infosheet for reopened streams

Name of the NBS		Reopened streams	
NBS Typology		Natural and semi-natural water bodies and hydrographic network	
Description	The complete coverage of a watercourse is undoubtedly the most traumatic human intervention that a river system can undergo since it results in the complete disappearance of the latter. It leads to the complete disappearance of the habitats, the riparian forest, the relations between the aquifer and the banks, etc., but also to a major ecological discontinuity of the fluvial network. Whenever the socio-political context allows it, the reopening of the stream should be realized. The opening of streams is necessarily accompanied by heavy demolition work and reconstruction of a new bed.		
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	N/A		N/A
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Increased habitat for biodiversity ○ Rebuilt soil structure with water ○ Soil improvement potential ○ Efficient stormwater handling ○ Water reclamation(reduction in water demand from supply system) ○ Increased infiltration/water storage, enhanced water retention capacity in the area ○ Reduced damages from drought ○ Increased evapotranspiration ○ Reduced energy need due to water reclamation (link between water and energy) ○ Stream flow variation 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Fuel usage and emissions from the machines at the reconstruction phase ○ Energy demand for water treatment ○ Construction material requirement ○ Chemical requirement for water treatment
City scale	Impact at city scale depends on continuity of the streams		N/A

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Avoided GHG emissions	GHG emissions released (N)	All GHG emitting processes including combustion, Energy generation, Transportation, Biogenic and anthropogenic	✓		kg CO ₂ eq/yr, kg CO ₂ eq/kg of product
Common air quality index	Air pollutants released from vehicles (N)	Transportation activities, Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation	✓		mg/ m ³ , ug/ m ³ , mg/ m ³ /d, ug/ m ³ /d, kg/ m ³ /yr
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for water supply (N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for water treatment (N)				
Raw material efficiency	Chemicals used for water treatment (N)	Water treatment, Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing processes for chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		g/d, kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
	Construction materials required (N)	Manufacturing of construction materials, Transportation construction materials	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Fuel consumption for vehicles (N)	Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation, Fuel combustion	✓		L/100 km, L/km, m ³ /yr, MJ/yr, kg/d, kg/yr
	Water demand for irrigation (N)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
	Water demand from supply system – for human consumption (N)	Water treatment, Pumping operation for water supply, Manufacturing and transportation of treatment chemicals, Energy generation, Disposal activities for treatment residues	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
	Water supply from alternative sources than supply system (N)	Pumping, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Soil quality	Organic matter content of soil (N)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/m ³
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Stormwater avoided into sewer (N)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		m ³ /yr
	Surface runoff – not captured by stormwater sewers (N)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Water scarcity	Water demand from supply system – for human consumption (N)	Water treatment, Pumping operation for water supply, Manufacturing and transportation of treatment chemicals, Energy generation, Disposal activities for treatment residues	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
	Water supply from alternative sources than supply system (N)	Pumping, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr

Table S36. System boundary infosheet for re-profiling river banks

Name of the NBS		Re-profiling river banks	
NBS Typology		Natural and semi-natural water bodies and hydrographic network	
Description			
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Rebuilt soil structure with water ○ Soil improvement potential, ○ Biodiversity, ○ Indirect water reclamation potential, ○ Reduction in urban heat island effect, ○ Positive impact on energy consumption of surrounding buildings due to cooling effect, ○ Reduced energy need due to water reclamation (link between water and energy), ○ Rainwater absorbed 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Fuel usage and emissions from the machines at the reconstruction phase ○ Consumption of fertilizers and chemicals for maintenance if vegetation is also present
Neighbourhood scale			
City scale			

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Building energy needs Cumulative energy demands Energy efficiency	Energy demand for cooling (O, N, C)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Common air quality index	Air pollutants released from vehicles (O, N, C)	Transportation activities, Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation		✓	mg/m ³ , ug/m ³ , mg/m ³ /d, ug/m ³ /d, kg/m ³ /yr
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for maintenance (N, C)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for water supply (N, C)				
Raw material efficiency	Fertilizers – chemical (O, N, C)	Fertilizer manufacturing, Fertilizer transport, Fertilizer spreading	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Fertilizers – organic (O, N, C)				
	Herbicides – chemical (O, N, C)	Herbicide manufacturing, Herbicide transportation, Herbicide application			
	Herbicides – organic (O, N, C)				
	Insecticides – chemical (O, N, C)	Insecticide manufacturing, Insecticide transport, Insecticide application			
	Insecticides – organic (O, N, C)				
	Pesticides – chemical (O, N, C)				

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
	Pesticides – organic (O, N, C)	Pesticide manufacturing, Pesticide transport, Pesticide application			
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Surface runoff - not captured by stormwater sewers (O, N, C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m3/d, m3/yr
Water quality	Water pollutants removed (O, N, C)	Water treatment, Phytoremediation, Energy generation, Chemical manufacturing and transport, Disposal activities for treatment residues	✓		mg/L, ug/L, kg/m3, kg/L, kg/yr

Table S37. System boundary infosheet for vegetation systems for riverbanks erosion control

Name of the NBS		Vegetation systems for riverbanks erosion control	
NBS Typology		Natural and semi-natural water bodies and hydrographic network	
Description		Soil bioengineering and biotechnical slope protection is the use of plants and plant materials (brush) to control erosion along streambanks. Vegetation engineering techniques can recreate technically and biologically functional natural banks using living plants as strengthening materials.	
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Flood and erosion protection, ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration, ○ Biodiversity, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Shock absorbers for heavy rainfall, ○ Decreased water turbidity, ○ Reduced flow velocities along eroding streambank ○ Deflected flow from the bank, ○ Rebuilt soil structure with water, ○ Soil improvement potential, ○ Indirect water reclamation potential, ○ Food production at local scale, ○ Avoidance of transported food (fuel savings, carbon savings), ○ Energy savings compared to grey, conventional alternatives (NBS replace other technologies and associated materials, energy consumption, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Fuel usage and emissions from the machines at the reconstruction phase ○ Increase in water consumption, ○ Potential requirement for additional fertilizers or other chemicals for maintenance of the vegetation
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Decreased water turbidity, 		
City scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Reduced flow velocities along eroding streambank ○ Deflected flow from the bank, ○ Rebuilt soil structure with water, ○ Soil improvement potential, ○ Indirect water reclamation potential, ○ Food production at local scale, ○ Avoidance of transported food (fuel savings, carbon savings), ○ Energy savings compared to grey, conventional alternatives (NBS replace other technologies and associated materials, energy consumption, etc.) 		

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Cumulative energy demands	Energy consumption avoided (O, N, C)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources		✓	J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for construction (O, N, C)		✓		
Per capita food production variability	Food supply - of plant origin (O, N, C)	Urban agriculture, Transportation of produce, Fuel consumption, Irrigation processes, Production and transportation of agricultural chemicals, Consumption of resources for maintenance, Conventional agriculture	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Raw material efficiency	Construction materials avoided (O, N, C)	Manufacturing of construction materials, Transportation construction materials	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Fuel consumption for vehicles (O)	Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation, Fuel combustion	✓		L/100 km, L/km, m3/yr, MJ/yr, kg/d, kg/yr

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
	Fertilizers – chemical (O, N, C)	Fertilizer manufacturing, Fertilizer transport, Fertilizer spreading	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Fertilizers – organic (O, N, C)				
	Herbicides – chemical (O, N, C)	Herbicide manufacturing, Herbicide transportation, Herbicide application			
	Herbicides – organic (O, N, C)				
	Insecticides – chemical (O, N, C)	Insecticide manufacturing, Insecticide transport, Insecticide application			
	Insecticides – organic (O, N, C)				
	Pesticides – chemical (O, N, C)	Pesticide manufacturing, Pesticide transport, Pesticide application			
	Pesticides – organic (O, N, C)				
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O, N, C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		m3/yr
	Surface runoff - not captured by stormwater sewers (O, N, C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m3/d, m3/yr
Water quality	Eroded soil into waterbodies (O, N, C)	Erosion process		✓	kg/yr, t/yr, m3/yr
Water scarcity	Water demand for irrigation (O)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m3/d, m3/yr

Table S38. System boundary infosheet for constructed wetland for phytoremediation-constructed wetland for wastewater treatment

Name of the NBS		Constructed wetland for phytoremediation Constructed wetland for wastewater treatment	
NBS Typology		Constructed wetlands and built structures for water management	
Description		This NBS essentially consists of the implementation of constructed wetlands (CWs). CWs are engineered wetlands that have been designed and constructed to make the most of natural processes for treating wastewater, but do so in a more controlled environment than natural wetlands. In urban environments, this NBS will provide a sustainable source of irrigation water, a new model of green/blue infrastructure or urban park at low cost and a support in the water management strategy of the city.	
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Purification of polluted waters (in small scales) ○ Biodiversity ○ Controlling soil erosion and stormwater 	N/A	
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Soil fertility ○ Avoidance of soil contamination ○ Reduced energy demand for irrigation 		
City scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Impact at this scale is limited 		

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for water supply (O, N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for water treatment (O, N)				
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for water supply (O, N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for water treatment (O, N)				
Raw material efficiency	Metals extracted from soil (O, N)	Extraction/recycling processes by plants, Conventional bioremediation technologies	✓		kg/yr, t/yr
	Water demand for irrigation (O, N)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Soil quality	Organic matter content of soil (O, N)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/m ³
	Toxic pollutants into soil (O, N)	All toxic pollutant generating processes	✓	✓	g PTE/yr, mg/ m ³ , ug/ m ³ , ng/ m ³ , mg/yr

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Surface runoff – not captured by stormwater sewers (O, N)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /yr
	Stormwater avoided into sewer (O, N)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Water quality	Toxic pollutants into water (O, N)	All toxic pollutant generating processes	✓	✓	mg/ m ³ , ug/ m ³ , ng/ m ³ , mg/yr
	Water pollutants removed (O, N)	Water treatment, Phytoremediation, Energy generation, Chemical manufacturing and transport, Disposal activities for treatment activities	✓		mg/L, ug/L, kg/ m ³ , kg/L, kg/yr
Water scarcity	Water supply from alternative sources than supply system	Pumping, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr

Table S39. System boundary infosheet for de-sealed areas

Name of the NBS		De-sealed areas	
NBS Typology		Constructed wetlands and built structures for water management	
Description		“De-sealing” consists in replacing impervious surfaces with more permeable surfaces, in order to recover major soil functions: water infiltration capacity, soil-atmosphere exchange, carbon storage, biodiversity, etc.	
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale			N/A
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks ○ Capture atmospheric CO2 during natural lighting hours ○ Decreased heat island effect (less heat storage) ○ Water reclamation, reduced runoff water volume ○ Increased water infiltration ○ Reduced flood effect ○ Increased flood protection ○ Decrease in rainwater volumes in unitary network(less water treatment) ○ Removal of contaminants in soil ○ Rebuilt soil structure with water ○ Potential for more fertile ground around the building ○ Soil improvement potential ○ Water reclamation 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Reduction of stock in organic matter of soil
City scale			N/A

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Avoided GHG emissions	GHG emissions avoided (N)	All GHG emitting processes including combustion, Energy generation, Transportation	✓	✓	kg CO ₂ eq/yr, kg CO ₂ eq/kg of product
Efficiency of valorisation as a resulting of recycling process	Waste recycled (N)	Recycling processes, Incineration process, Composting, Energy generation, Water pumping and treatment	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for water treatment (N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Raw material efficiency	Other resource (N, C)	All relevant processes producing or consuming resources not specified elsewhere in the list	✓	✓	kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
	Water supply from alternative sources than supply system (N)	Pumping, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Soil quality	Organic matter content of soil (N)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/m ³
	Soil pollutants removed (N)	Soil remediation, Phytoremediation, Bioremediation	✓		kg/ m ³ , kg/ m ³ /yr
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Stormwater avoided into sewer (N)	Wastewater treatment, manufacturing of chemicals, transportation of chemicals	✓		m ³ /yr
	Surface run-off – not captured by stormwater sewers (N)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Water scarcity	Water supply from alternative sources than supply system (N)	Pumping, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr

Table S40. System boundary infosheet for rain/infiltration gardens

Name of the NBS		Rain/infiltration gardens	
NBS Typology		Constructed wetlands and built structures for water management	
Description	A rain garden is a depressed area in the landscape that collects rain water from a roof, driveway or street and allows it to soak into the ground. Planted with grasses and flowering perennials, rain gardens can be a cost effective and beautiful way to reduce runoff from your property. Rain gardens can also help filter out pollutants in runoff and provide food and shelter for butterflies, song birds and other wildlife.		
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks ○ Capture atmospheric CO2 during natural lighting hours ○ Water reclamation ○ Reduction in water demand from supply system ○ Reduced load from run-off into sewerage systems ○ Filters pollutants and sediments ○ Removal of urban pollutants through infiltration and vegetative filtering ○ Rebuilt soil structure with water ○ Potential for more fertile ground around the building 		N/A
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Water reclamation ○ Reduction in water demand from supply system ○ Reduced load from run-off into sewerage systems ○ Filters pollutants and sediments ○ Removal of urban pollutants through infiltration and vegetative filtering ○ Rebuilt soil structure with water ○ Potential for more fertile ground around the building 		N/A
City scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Water reclamation ○ Reduction in water demand from supply system ○ Reduced load from run-off into sewerage systems ○ Filters pollutants and sediments ○ Removal of urban pollutants through infiltration and vegetative filtering ○ Rebuilt soil structure with water ○ Potential for more fertile ground around the building 		N/A

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO ₂ sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO ₂ eq/10 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq/100 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq per amount of biomass
Raw material efficiency	Food supply – of plant origin (O, N)	Urban agriculture, Transportation of produce, Fuel consumption, Irrigation processes, Production and transportation of agricultural chemicals, Consumption of resources for maintenance, Conventional farming activities	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Water demand for irrigation (O, N, C)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Soil quality	Soil pollutants removed (O, N, C)	Soil remediation, Phytoremediation, Bioemediation	✓		kg/m ³ , kg/ m ³ /yr

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Surface runoff not captured by stormwater sewers (O, N, C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O, N, C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		m ³ /yr
Water quality	Water pollutants removed (O, N, C)	Water treatment, Phytoremediation, Energy generation, Chemical manufacturing and transport, Disposal activities for treatment residues	✓		mg/L, ug/L, kg/ m ³ , kg/L, kg/yr
Water scarcity	Water demand from supply system - for human consumption (O, N, C)	Water treatment, Pumping operation for water supply, Manufacturing and transportation of treatment chemicals, Energy generation, Disposal activities for treatment residues	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O, N, C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		m ³ /yr

Table S41. System boundary infosheet for swales

Name of the NBS		Swales	
NBS Typology		Constructed wetlands and built structures for water management	
Description		Swales are broad, shallow, earthen channels designed to slow runoff, promote infiltration, and filter pollutants and sediments in the process of conveying runoff. Swales are often densely planted with a variety of trees, shrubs, and grasses along the bottom and sides of the channel.	
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Water reclamation, ○ Reduction in water demand from supply system, ○ Reduced load from run-off into sewerage systems, 		
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Removal of urban pollutants through infiltration and vegetative filtering, ○ Rebuilt soil structure with water, ○ Potential for more fertile ground around the building, ○ Soil improvement potential, ○ Biodiversity, ○ Food supply (if vegetated swales) 		
City scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Water reclamation, ○ Reduction in water demand from supply system, ○ Reduced load from run-off into sewerage systems, ○ Food supply (if vegetated swales) 		

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for water supply (O,N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Raw material efficiency	Food supply - of plant origin (if vegetated swales is applied) (O, N, C)	Urban agriculture, Transportation of produce, Fuel consumption, Irrigation processes, Production and transportation of agricultural chemicals, Consumption of resources for maintenance, Conventional farming activities	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Soil quality	Soil pollutants removed (O, N)	Soil remediation, Phytoremediation, Bioremediation	✓		kg/m3, kg/m3/yr
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O, N, C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		m3/yr

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
	Surface runoff - not captured by stormwater sewers (O, N, C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended			m3/d, m3/yr
Water quality	Toxic pollutants into water (O, N)	All toxic pollutant generating processes	✓		mg/m3, ug/m3, ng/m3, mg/yr
Water scarcity	Water supply from alternative sources than supply system (O, N)	Pumping, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m3/d, m3/yr

Table S42. System boundary infosheet for use of terraces

Name of the NBS		Use of terraces	
NBS Typology		Constructed wetlands and built structures for water management	
Description	<p>Terracing is a form of mechanical soil conservation method, generally intended to control erosion and surface runoff. Terraces are constructed to fulfil multiple functions. Most important ones:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – reduce surface erosion through the shortening of the rout and reducing the speed of the runoff and sediments on the ground surface, increase the surface water retention via storage of precipitation or melt waters, – reduce the flood hazard, – increase the groundwater resources due to the infiltration of certain amounts of water stored in the frontal dyke of a terrace, – decrease the risk of ravine formation 		
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Aesthetics ○ Water reclamation potential ○ Biodiversity 		N/A
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Reduction of erosion ○ Water reclamation 		N/A
City scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Reduction in water demand from supply system ○ Reduced load from run-off into sewerage system ○ Food supply 		N/A

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for water supply (O, N, C)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Per capita food production variability	Food supply – of plant origin (C)	Urban agriculture, Transportation of produce, Fuel consumption, Irrigation processes, Production and transportation of agricultural chemicals, Consumption of resources for maintenance, Conventional farming activities	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Raw material efficiency	Food supply – of plant origin (O, N, C)	Urban agriculture, Transportation of produce, Fuel consumption, Irrigation processes, Production and transportation of agricultural chemicals, Consumption of resources for maintenance, Conventional farming activities	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Water demand from supply system - for human consumption (O, N, C)	Water treatment, Pumping operation for water supply, Manufacturing and transportation of	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
		treatment chemicals, Energy generation, Disposal activities for treatment residues			
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Surface runoff - not captured by stormwater sewers (O, N, C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Water scarcity	Water demand from supply system - for human consumption (O, N, C)	Water treatment, Pumping operation for water supply, Manufacturing and transportation of treatment chemicals, Energy generation, Disposal activities for treatment residues	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Water quality	Eroded soil into waterbodies (O, N, C)	Erosion process		✓	kg/yr, t/yr, m ³ /yr

On Building Structures

Table S43. System boundary infosheet for extensive green roofs

Name of the NBS		Extensive green roofs	
NBS Typology		Green roofs	
Description	Green roofs serve several purposes for a building, such as absorbing rainwater (Simmons et al., 2008), providing insulation (Alexandri and Jones, 2008), creating a habitat for wildlife (Nagase and Tashiro-Ishii, 2018), increasing benevolence and decreasing stress of the people around the roof by providing a more aesthetically pleasing landscape (Ragheb et al., 2016), and helping to lower urban air temperatures and mitigate the heat island effect (Jin et al., 2018). Extensive green roofs are generally made up of a very thin layer of substrate (from 8 cm to 15 cm) or other planting medium with shallow-root plants like sedum, herbs, mosses, and grasses. This solution requires a minimal maintenance and it normally is not occupied. Often, green roofs substrate is contained by a tray system, which provides a barrier to excessive growth, protects the roof membrane, and interlocks the entire system together to prevent wind damage.		
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks, ○ Capture of atmospheric CO2 during natural lighting hours, ○ Aesthetics, ○ Reduced heat island effect, ○ Water reclamation potential, ○ Can be used in synergy with roof ponds, ○ Rainwater collection, ○ Biodiversity, ○ Decrease total nitrogen in runoff 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Maintenance requirements (irrigation water, energy demand and fertilizers)
Neighbourhood scale			
City scale			

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO2 sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO2 eq/10 yrs, kg CO2 eq/100 yrs, kg CO2 eq per amount of biomass
Avoided GHG emissions	GHG emissions avoided (O)	All GHG emitting processes including combustion, Energy generation, Transportation		✓	kg CO2 eq/yr, kg CO2 eq/kg of product
Building energy needs	Energy demand for cooling (O)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for heating (O)				

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Common air quality index	Air pollutants removed (O, N, C)	Direct capture by leaves, NOx and PM capture	✓	✓	µg/m3, mg/m3, kg/year
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for cooling (O)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for heating (O)				
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for cooling (O)				
	Energy demand for heating (O)				
	Energy demand for maintenance (O)				
Raw material efficiency	Energy demand for water supply (O)				
	Fertilizers – chemical (O)	Fertilizer manufacturing, Fertilizer transport, Fertilizer spreading	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Fertilizers – organic (O)				
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Water demand for irrigation (O)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m3/d, m3/yr
	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		m3/yr
Surface runoff - not captured by stormwater sewers (O)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	m3/d, m3/yr			
Water scarcity	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		m3/yr
	Water demand for irrigation (O)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m3/d, m3/yr

Table S44. System boundary infosheet for intensive/semi-intensive green roofs

Name of the NBS		Intensive green roofs Semi-intensive green roofs	
NBS Typology		Green roofs	
Description		<p>Roofs do not all have the same carrying capacity, therefore depending on the structures, and the type of plantation must be adapted. Intensive green roofs (living roof) are those with the more substrate, usually with a total thickness starting by app. 20 to 200 cm, therefore the stress imposed on the structure is very large. Usually, either roofs that have an intensive green roof were planned to accommodate the green roof at the time of the construction of the building or there have been structure reinforcement works. An intensive green roof weighs from 170 kg m⁻² to over 970 kg m⁻², then given the large amount of soil, plant options are extremely large, ranging from shrubs to urban agriculture to trees.(32) Since the plants are large gauges, it requires an irrigation system and major maintenance. Often, intensive green roofs can serve as parks open to the public.</p> <p>A semi-intensive green roof system is characterized by small herbaceous plants, ground covers, grasses and small shrubs, requiring moderate maintenance and occasional irrigation. A typical growing medium depth for a semi-intensive green roof is 15 to 30 cm. This system is able to retain more storm water than an extensive system and provides the potential to host a richer ecology. Though higher in maintenance, this green roof system also provides the potential for a formal and intensive garden effect. In addition, few references identify a third category of green roofs: simple-intensive (semi-intensive) (FLL, 2008) which are vegetated with lawns and ground covering plants. These roofs require frequent maintenance including cutting, watering, and fertilization.</p>	
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Aesthetics, o Insulation, o Reduced heat island effect, o Reduced energy demand for cooling, o Water reclamation potential, o Can be used in synergy with roof ponds, o Urban farming practices (foods&vegetables), o Rainwater collection (infiltration), o Biodiversity, o Avoided transportation of food in case of farming practices (fuel and carbon savings), o Low reduced common air quality index background levels (low RED_CAI_BGL) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Maintenance requirements (irrigation water and energy demand) 	
Neighbourhood scale			
City scale			

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO2 sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO2 eq/10 yrs, kg CO2 eq/100 yrs, kg CO2 eq per amount of biomass
Avoided GHG emissions	GHG emissions avoided (O)	All GHG emitting processes including combustion, Energy generation, Transportation		✓	kg CO2 eq/yr, kg CO2 eq/kg of product
Building energy needs	Energy demand for cooling (O)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for heating (O)				
Common air quality index	Air pollutants removed (O, N, C)	Direct capture by leaves, NOx and PM capture	✓	✓	µg/m3, mg/m3, kg/year
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for cooling (O)				
	Energy demand for heating (O)				
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for cooling (O)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for heating (O)				
	Energy demand for maintenance (O)				
	Energy demand for water supply (O)				
Peak flow variation	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		m3/yr
Per capita food production variability	Food supply – of plant origin (O)	Urban agriculture, Transportation of produce, Fuel consumption, Irrigation processes, Production and transportation of agricultural chemicals, Consumption of resources for maintenance, Conventional farming activities	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Raw material efficiency	Fertilizers – chemical (O)	Fertilizer manufacturing, Fertilizer transport, Fertilizer spreading	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Fertilizers – organic (O)				
	Food supply – of plant origin (O)	Urban agriculture, Transportation of produce, Fuel consumption, Irrigation processes, Production and transportation of agricultural chemicals, Consumption of resources for maintenance, Conventional farming activities	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		m3/yr
	Water demand for irrigation (O)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m3/d, m3/yr
	Water supply from alternative sources than supply system (O)	Pumping, Water treatment if necessary	✓		

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals			m3/yr
	Surface runoff - not captured by stormwater sewers (O)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m3/d, m3/yr
Water scarcity	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		m3/yr
	Water demand for irrigation (O)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m3/d, m3/yr
	Water supply from alternative sources than supply system (O)	Pumping, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m3/d, m3/yr

Table S45. System boundary infosheet for roof ponds

Name of the NBS		Roof ponds
NBS Typology		Green roofs
Description		
Narrative impacts		Positive
		Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks and capture atmospheric CO2 during natural lighting hours, ○ Envelope and insulation improvement, ○ Heat island effect reduction, 	
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Heating and cooling demand reduction, ○ Aesthetics, ○ Water reclamation potential, ○ Can be used in synergy with roof top gardens to supply water for dry soil ○ Rainwater collection, ○ Biodiversity, ○ Increased soil surface ○ Water savings (other raw material consumptions should be analysed) 	
City scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Increased soil surface, ○ Aesthetic, ○ Can be used with rooftop gardens to supply water for dry soil, ○ Insulation, ○ Reduction in urban heat island effect: reduces energy needs in the building 	

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO2 sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O, N, C)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO2 eq/10 yrs, kg CO2 eq/100 yrs, kg CO2 eq per amount of biomass
Avoided GHG emissions	GHG emissions avoided (O, N, C)	All GHG emitting processes including combustion, Energy generation, Transportation	✓	✓	kg CO2 eq/yr, kg CO2 eq/kg of product
Building energy needs	Energy demand for cooling (O, N, C) Energy demand for heating (O, N, C)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, Kwh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for cooling (O, N, C) Energy demand for heating (O, N, C)				
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for cooling (O, N, C) Energy demand for heating (O, N, C)				
	Energy demand for water supply (O, N, C)				

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Raw material efficiency	Water demand for irrigation (O, N)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓	✓ (storage in pumps)	L/hr, L/d, m3/d, m3/yr
	Water supply from alternative sources than supply system (O, N)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m3/d, m3/yr
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		m3/yr
	Surface runoff - not captured by stormwater sewers (O)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m3/d, m3/yr
Water scarcity	Water supply from alternative sources than supply system (O, N)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m3/d, m3/yr

Table S46. System boundary infosheet for climber green walls

Name of the NBS		Climber green walls	
NBS Typology		Vertical structures “green walls and façades”	
Description		This NBS type is about the use of self-climbing plants to cover walls and façades. By this characteristic type, the plant is directly rooted into soil. This is the easiest, cheapest and most efficient way for greening walls and buildings with a long tradition and history back to ancient times (Ottelle, 2011).	
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Isolation, ○ Reduced heat island effect reducing building cooling energy demands, ○ Reduced fuel and electricity demand for cooling energy, ○ Contribution to filtration of air pollutants, ○ Carbon sequestration, ○ Aesthetics, ○ Biodiversity, ○ Plants can be composted, ○ Woods can be recycled ○ Low Reduced common air quality index background levels (Low_CAI_BGL) 		Water for maintenance may be needed.
Neighbourhood scale			
City scale			

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO2 sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O, N)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO2 eq/10 yrs, kg CO2 eq/100 yrs, kg CO2 eq per amount of biomass
Avoided GHG emissions	GHG emissions avoided (O, N)	All GHG emitting processes including combustion, Energy generation, Transportation		✓	kg CO2 eq/yr, kg CO2 eq/kg of product
Building energy needs	Energy demand for cooling (O)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for heating (O)				
Common air quality index	Air pollutants removed (O, N)	Direct capture by leaves, NOx and PM capture		✓	µg/m3, mg/m3, kg/year
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for cooling (O)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for heating (O)				
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for cooling (O)				

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
	Energy demand for heating (O)				
Raw material efficiency	Compost (O)	Composting, Energy generation, Fuel consumption, Water consumption, Transportation	✓		kg/yr, t/yr
	Fuel consumption avoided (O, N)	Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation, Fuel combustion	✓		L/100 km, L/km, m3/yr, MJ/yr, kg/d, kg/yr
	Water demand for irrigation (O)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m3/d, m3/yr
Water scarcity	Water demand for irrigation (O)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m3/d, m3/yr

Table S47. System boundary infosheet for living wall systems-build or attached planter systems

Name of the NBS		Living wall systems Build or attached planter systems	
NBS Typology		Vertical structures “green walls and facades”	
Description			
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks, ○ Capture of atmospheric CO2 during natural lighting hours ○ Reduced heating of walls, ○ Insulation, ○ Reduction in urban heat island effect: reduces energy needs in the building, ○ Fuel savings via the decreased heating/cooling energy demand ○ Storm/rain water runoff reduction (rain water is collected in a storage and then can be used for irrigation in living wall systems), ○ Low reduced common air quality index background levels 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Possible resource consumption for maintenance including chemicals and irrigation water (if irrigation water cannot be supplied by rain/storm water collected) 	
Neighbourhood scale	CO2 capture, lower atmospheric CO2		
City scale	CO2 capture, lower atmospheric CO2, 'limited impact, limited food production		

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO2 sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O, N)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO2 eq/10 yrs, kg CO2 eq/100 yrs, kg CO2 eq per amount of biomass
Avoided GHG emissions	GHG emissions avoided (O, N)	All GHG emitting processes including combustion, Energy generation, Transportation		✓	kg CO2 eq/yr, kg CO2 eq/kg of product
Building energy needs	Energy demand for cooling (O)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for heating (O)				
Common air quality index	Air pollutants removed (O, N)	Direct capture by leaves, NOx and PM capture		✓	µg/m3, mg/m3, kg/year
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for air treatment (O)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for cooling (O)				
	Energy demand for heating (O)				
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for air treatment (O)				

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
	Energy demand for cooling (O)				
	Energy demand for heating (O)				
Per capita food production variability	Food supply - of plant origin (C)	Urban agriculture, Transportation of produce, Fuel consumption, Irrigation processes, Production and transportation of agricultural chemicals, Consumption of resources for maintenance, Conventional agriculture	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Food supply - of plant origin (C)	Urban agriculture, Transportation of produce, Fuel consumption, Irrigation processes, Production and transportation of agricultural chemicals, Consumption of resources for maintenance, Conventional agriculture	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Fuel consumption avoided (O)	Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation, Fuel combustion	✓		L/100 km, L/km, m3/yr, MJ/yr, kg/d, kg/yr
Raw material efficiency	Fertilizers – chemical (O, N, C)	Fertilizer manufacturing, Fertilizer transport, Fertilizer spreading	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Fertilizers – organic (O, N, C)				
	Herbicides – chemical (O, N, C)	Herbicide manufacturing, Herbicide transportation, Herbicide application			
	Herbicides – organic (O, N, C)				
	Insecticides – chemical (O, N, C)	Insecticide manufacturing, Insecticide transport, Insecticide application			
	Insecticides – organic (O, N, C)				
	Pesticides – chemical (O, N, C)	Pesticide manufacturing, Pesticide transport, Pesticide application			
	Pesticides – organic (O, N, C)				
Water scarcity	Water demand for irrigation (O)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m3/d, m3/yr

Urban Green Space Management

Table S48. System boundary infosheet for as much as possible keeping old trees

Name of the NBS		As much as possible keeping old trees	
NBS Typology		Direct human interventions	
Description	An old tree has multiple benefits on its surroundings: it reflects history, thus arouse respect towards nature, even in little children; as it can be several hundred year old it lived through several smaller or bigger local climate change and has a well adapting ability and because of this reason it is an extremely important source of seedlings. Old trees have essential role in an ecosystem, thus they cannot be replaced by any artificial tools or methods. They give shelter, breeding and sleeping place for numerous animal species. They connected to the elements of an ecosystem with uncountable strings. The really old standalone trees are usually under nature conservation or local protection.		
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks, ○ Capture of atmospheric CO₂ during natural lighting hours ○ Heat island effect reduction, ○ Wide scale of biodiversity, ○ Aesthetic, ○ Flood protection, ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration, ○ Certain tree species can reduce water supply due to evapotranspiration (benefit in regions prone to flooding but problem in arid or semi-arid regions) 		
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ CO₂ capture, ○ Heat island effect reduction, 		
City scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Flood protection 		

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO ₂ sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O, N, C)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO ₂ eq/10 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq/100 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq per amount of biomass
Avoided GHG emissions	GHG emissions avoided (O, N, C)	All GHG emitting processes including combustion, Energy generation, Transportation	✓	✓	kg CO ₂ eq/yr, kg CO ₂ eq/kg of product
Common air quality index	Air pollutants removed (O, N, C)	Direct capture by leaves, NO _x and PM captures	✓		µg/ m ³ , mg/ m ³ , kg/year
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for cooling (O, N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for cooling (O, N)				

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Soil quality	Organic matter content of soil (O, N)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/m ³
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Surface runoff – not captured by stormwater sewers (O, N, C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr

Table S49. System boundary infosheet for composting

Name of the NBS		Composting	
NBS Typology		Direct human interventions	
Description	<p>Composting is a natural method for processing solid waste in which organic material is broken down by microorganisms in the presence of oxygen to a point where it can be safely stored, handled and applied to the environment as a fertilizer and soil amendment. Organic material has a twofold origin:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Community: urban allotments, small-scale urban livestock, nearby restaurants, markets, fruit stores, etc. – Industry processes: crops or agro-industry waste. <p>The objective is to close the loop on organics recovery. Likewise, this NBS has educational and engagement purposes. It could be helped by chickens because chickens clean the compost of weeds, rodents and insects, while the compost helps to warm the animals and feed the birds.</p>		
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Soil improvement potential but depends on the soil structure and organisms in the soil ○ Lower daily production of waste ○ Improved soil structure ○ Water and nutrient retainment ○ Improved crop yields and pastures ○ Plants with deeper root systems, healthy plants 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Water for maintenance ○ Energy demand for maintenance and processing of waste
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Soil improvement potential but depends on the soil structure and organisms in the soil ○ Lower daily production of waste, "zero waste" production: loop-flows at neighbourhood scale (e.g. compost for communal gardens) ○ Recycling and use of recycled materials, value chain ○ Reduced pesticide and synthetic fertiliser use 		N/A
City scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Soil improvement potential but depends on the soil structure and organisms in the soil ○ Lower daily production of waste ○ Recycling and use of recycled materials, value chain ○ Reduced pesticide and synthetic fertiliser use 		N/A

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Cumulative energy demand	Compost (O, N)	Composting, Energy generation, Fuel consumption, Water consumption, Transportation	✓		kg/yr, t/yr
	Energy demand for processing of waste to be used as a resource (O)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Efficiency of valorisation as a result of recycling process	Waste recycled (N, C)	Recycling processes, Incineration process, Composting, Energy generation, Water pumping and treatment	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for maintenance (O)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for processing of waste to be used as a resource (O)				
Material circularity indicator	Waste recycled (N, C)	Recycling processes, Incineration process, Composting, Energy generation, Water pumping and treatment	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Raw material efficiency	Fertilizers avoided (N, C)	Fertilizer manufacturing, Fertilizer transport, Fertilizer spreading	✓	✓	kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Other resource (N, C)	All relevant processes producing or consuming resources not specified elsewhere in the list	✓	✓	kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Pesticides avoided (N, C)	Pesticide manufacturing, Pesticide transport, Pesticide application	✓	✓	kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Water for maintenance (O)	Pumping operations, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Soil quality	Organic matter content of soil (N, C)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/m ³
Specific waste generation	Waste generated (N, C)	All waste generating processes	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Water scarcity	Water for maintenance (O)	Pumping operations, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr

Table S50. System boundary infosheet for conserving dead wood on the ground

Name of the NBS		Conserving dead wood on the ground	
NBS Typology		Direct human interventions	
Description	In a forest ecosystem deadwoods are playing an essential role. They give a natural shelter, breeding and feeding place for a very diverse fauna and even for fungus. Bats and other small mammals use them for day-sleeping shelter, for birds feeding and breeding place, while bugs like stag-beetle or rhinoceros beetle live almost their whole life in a decaying wood. Generally, deadwood is the final stage of a tree, when all the nutrient circulation is stopped, however the process can take several years. In a closed canopy forest or woods those trees which lack behind in the competition for light can die or the old trees which are not as vital as the young ones. In deadwoods pest insects can find shelter as well, but they can be the nutrient of birds or other bugs. Therefore, in a habitat where deadwood can be found the balance of nature is dynamic, but without them an essential nutrient source is missing from the system. Normally it is a natural process to become dead, so this NBS should be used only in woody area, without transporting trees from one place to another. Green space managers can use this NBS as a trump card for balancing woody ecosystems in a long-term scenario.		
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Biodiversity, ○ Providing habitat for several species playing important role in recycling nutrients in forests and woodland ecosystems, ○ Improving material waste management through reuse of dead wood, pruning waste, stones, pottery fragments, etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Possible resource and energy consumption for processing dead wood into usable products; ○ Harmful insects can find shelter in the dead wood and can disperse from them, but in a well-functioning ecosystem they are necessary as well. 	
Neighbourhood scale	N/A	N/A	
City scale	N/A	N/A	

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for processing of waste to be used as a resource (O)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Harvest levels of wood resources	Biomass (O)	Composting, Energy generation		✓	kg/m3/d, t/m3/yr, kg/m2/yr, GJ/yr
Material circularity indicator	Waste recycled (O, N, C)	Recycling processes, Incineration process, Composting, Energy generation, Water pumping and treatment,	✓	✓	kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Raw material efficiency	Fuel consumption for vehicles (O, N, C)	Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation, Fuel combustion	✓		L/100 km, L/km, m3/yr, MJ/yr, kg/d, kg/yr
	Other resource (O, N, C)	All relevant processes producing or consuming resources not specified elsewhere in the list	✓	✓	kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Soil quality	Nutrients to soil (O)	Agricultural processes, Urban farming processes, Manufacturing industry, NBS maintenance	✓	✓	kg/ha, g nutrient/kg soil, mg/L

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Specific waste generation	Waste recycled (O, N, C)	Recycling processes, Incineration process, Composting, Energy generation, Water pumping and treatment,	✓	✓	kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr

Table S51. System boundary infosheet for eco management plans/No management/Limited number of management interventions in time/specific positioning of management interventions in time

Name of the NBS		Eco management plans No management Limited number of management interventions in time Specific positioning of management interventions in time	
NBS Typology		Direct human interventions	
Description			
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	Actions can be taken for <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Avoided GHG emissions, ○ Sustainable land use, ○ Rebuilt soil structure, ○ Aesthetics ○ Biodiversity 		By applying these kind of management types in the first years, harmful insects may overpopulate. It takes time to reach the dynamic equilibrium of a near natural ecosystem. From economic point of view, an area with eco management plan is going to be less profitable in short term, then an intensively utilized.
Neighbourhood scale			
City scale			

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Avoided GHG emissions	GHG emissions avoided (O, N, C)	All GHG emitting processes including combustion, Energy generation, Transportation	✓	✓	kg CO2 eq/yr, kg CO2 eq/kg of product
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for maintenance (C)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Raw material efficiency	Fertilizers avoided (O, N, C) Herbicides avoided (O, N, C)	Fertilizer manufacturing, Fertilizer transport, Fertilizer spreading	✓		t/yr, m3/yr
		Herbicide manufacturing, Herbicide transportation, Herbicide application			

Table S52. System boundary infosheet for mulching

Name of the NBS		Mulching	
NBS Typology		Direct human interventions	
Description	Mulching is a technique used in plantations and maintenance that consists in covering the surface of the soil with an organic, mineral or plastic material in a continuous (film) or discontinuous way (grains, fragments, etc.) to protect the ground and plants mainly against weeds and soil evaporation. Originally, the term was created in 1935 to designate the action of mulching the soil (Loreau, 2014). In addition, mulching is one promising technology that is an integral component of conservation farming and is increasingly seen in the light of integrated soil management—an essential building stone for sustainable agriculture. The use of mulch has great agro-ecological potential—it typically conserves the soil, improves the soil ecology, stabilizes and enhances crop yield and provides various environmental services (Erenstein, 2003).		
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Flood and erosion protection ○ Water supply through improving soil infiltration ○ Biodiversity ○ Soil carbon storage ○ Increased soil quality ○ Biodiversity ○ Waste management (if waste is used for amelioration) ○ Potential for increased food production ○ Increased filter capacity ○ Habitat for soil organisms ○ Soil fertility ○ Water holding capacity ○ Mulching soil can help keep it moist in between rain or irrigation ○ Carbon sequestration ○ Higher food production potential with the improved soil quality ○ Increased nutrients in the soil ○ Water reclamation ○ Reduction in water demand from supply system ○ Reduced load from run-off into sewerage systems 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Increase in surface runoff for impermeable mulches ○ Increase unwanted chemicals in soil
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Carbon sequestration ○ Higher food production potential with the improved soil quality ○ Increased nutrients in the soil 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Energy demand for cutting of wood ○ Fuel consumption during transportation ○ Air pollutants released
City scale	N/A		N/A

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Avoided GHG emissions	GHG emissions released (O)	All GHG emitting processes including combustion, Energy generation, Transportation, Biogenic and anthropogenic	✓		kg CO ₂ eq/yr, kg CO ₂ eq/kg of product

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Common air quality index	Air pollutants released from vehicles (O)	Transportation activities, Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation	✓		mg/ m ³ , ug/ m ³ , mg/ m ³ /d, ug/ m ³ /d, kg/ m ³ /yr
Efficiency of valorisation as a result of recycling process	Waste recycled (O, N, C)	Recycling processes, Incineration process, Composting, Energy generation, Water pumping and treatment	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Material circularity indicator	Waste recycled (O)	Recycling processes, Incineration process, Composting, Energy generation, Water pumping and treatment	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Raw material efficiency	Food supply – of plant origin (O, N)	Urban agriculture, Transportation of produce, Fuel consumption, Irrigation processes, Production and transportation of agricultural chemicals, Consumption of resources for maintenance, Conventional farming activities	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Fuel consumption for vehicles (N)	Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation, Fuel combustion	✓		L/100 km, L/km, m ³ /yr, MJ/yr
	Other resource (O, N)	All relevant processes producing or consuming resources not specified elsewhere in the list	✓	✓	kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Soil quality	Chemicals avoided (O)	Manufacturing processes for chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, Treatment processes for medium contaminated with chemicals		✓	g/d, kg/d, kg/yr, ton/yr
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Stormwater avoided into the sewer	Wastewater treatment, manufacturing of chemicals, transportation of chemicals	✓		m ³ /yr
	Surface runoff – not captured by stormwater sewers	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
	Surface runoff – not captured by stormwater sewers	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr

Table S53. System boundary infosheet for reasoned or no use of chemical fertilizers

Name of the NBS		Reasoned or no use of chemical fertilizers (Sustainable use of fertilizer)	
NBS Typology		Direct human interventions	
Description	Sustainable use of fertilisers (SUF) is a nature-based strategy that combines a limited use of mineral fertiliser, the promoted use of organic fertilisers or/and biostimulants, the consideration of soil properties and soil biology. The decision on quantities of inputs used is taken in a balanced and integrated way. Sometimes the use of fertilisers may not be necessary. SUF aims at minimizing the economical and environmental costs of fertilisation practices such as use of fossil energies, water eutrophication, soil contamination, loss of biodiversity, sensitivity to pests. Fertiliser means “material, the main function of which is to provide nutrients for plants.”[Regulation (EC) 2003/2003]. Soil enrichment products are not considered as fertilisers.		
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ GHG emissions avoided in product manufacturing and use ○ Soil improvement potential but depends on the soil structure and organisms in the soil ○ Reduced use of chemicals ○ Avoided production of fertilizers and pesticides 		N/A
Neighbourhood scale			N/A
City scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ GHG emissions avoided in product manufacturing and use ○ Soil improvement potential but depends on the soil structure and organisms in the soil ○ Reduced use of chemicals ○ Avoided production of fertilizers and pesticides ○ Optimized production 		N/A

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Avoided GHG emissions	GHG emissions avoided (O)	All GHG emitting processes including combustion, Energy generation, Transportation	✓	✓	kg CO ₂ eq/yr, kg CO ₂ eq/kg of product
Common air quality index	Air pollutants released from vehicles (O)	Transportation activities, Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation	✓		mg/m ³ , ug/ m ³ , mg/ m ³ /d, ug/ m ³ /d, kg/ m ³ /yr
Cumulative energy demands	Energy consumption avoided (O)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓	✓	J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Per capita food production variability	Food supply – of plant origin (C)	Urban agriculture, Transportation of produce, Fuel consumption, Irrigation processes, Production and transportation of agricultural chemicals, Consumption of resources for maintenance, Conventional farming activities	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Raw material efficiency	Fuel consumption avoided (C)	Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation, Fuel combustion	✓		L/100 km, L/km, m ³ /yr, MJ/yr, kg/d, kg/yr
	Fuel consumption for vehicles (C)	Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation, Fuel combustion	✓		L/100 km, L/km, m ³ /yr, MJ/yr, kg/d, kg/yr
Soil quality	Fertilizers-chemical (O)	Fertilizer manufacturing, Fertilizer transport, Fertilizer spreading	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Specific waste generation	Waste generated (O)	All waste generating processes	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Water quality	Nutrients to waterbodies causing eutrophication (O)	Agricultural processes, Urban farming processes, Manufacturing industry	✓	✓	mg P/L, kg P/yr, mg N/L, kg N/L

Table S54. System boundary infosheet for reasoned use of organic fertilizer

Name of the NBS		Reasoned use of organic fertilizer (Sustainable use of fertilizer)	
NBS Typology		Direct human interventions	
Description	Sustainable use of fertilisers (SUF) is a nature-based strategy that combines a limited use of mineral fertiliser, the promoted use of organic fertilisers or/and biostimulants, the consideration of soil properties and soil biology. The decision on quantities of inputs used is taken in a balanced and integrated way. Sometimes the use of fertilisers may not be necessary. SUF aims at minimizing the economical and environmental costs of fertilisation practices such as use of fossil energies, water eutrophication, soil contamination, loss of biodiversity, sensitivity to pests. Fertiliser means “material, the main function of which is to provide nutrients for plants.”[Regulation (EC) 2003/2003]. Soil enrichment products are not considered as fertilisers.		
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Soil improvement potential but depends on the soil structure and organisms in the soil ○ Saving from organic fertilizers ○ Avoided production of fertilizers and pesticides ○ Optimized production 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Transportation of fertilizers
Neighbourhood scale			N/A
City scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Soil improvement potential but depends on the soil structure and organisms in the soil ○ Saving from organic fertilizers ○ Avoided production of fertilizers and pesticides ○ Optimized production 		N/A

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Avoided GHG emissions	GHG emissions released (O)	All GHG emitting processes including combustion, Energy generation, Transportation, Biogenic and anthropogenic	✓		kg CO ₂ eq/yr, kg CO ₂ eq/kg of product
Common air quality index	Air pollutants released from vehicles (O)	Transportation activities, Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation	✓		mg/m ³ , ug/ m ³ , mg/ m ³ /d, ug/ m ³ /d, kg/ m ³ /yr
Cumulative energy demands	Energy consumption avoided (O)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓	✓	J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Efficiency of valorisation as a result of recycling process	Waste recycled (O)	Recycling processes, Incineration process, Composting, Energy generation, Water pumping and treatment	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Per capita food production variability	Food supply – of plant origin (C)	Urban agriculture, Transportation of produce, Fuel consumption, Irrigation processes, Production and transportation of agricultural chemicals, Consumption	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
		of resources for maintenance, Conventional farming activities			
Raw material efficiency	Fuel consumption avoided (C)	Fuel extraction, Fuel refining and processing, Fuel transportation, Fuel combustion	✓		L/100 km, L/km, m ³ /yr, MJ/yr, kg/d, kg/yr
	Other resource (O, N)	All relevant processes producing or consuming resources not specified elsewhere in the list	✓	✓	kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Soil quality	Fertilizers-organic (O)	Fertilizer manufacturing, Fertilizer transport, Fertilizer spreading	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Specific waste generation	Waste generated (O)	All waste generating processes	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Water quality	Nutrients to waterbodies causing eutrophication (O)	Agricultural processes, Urban farming processes, Manufacturing industry	✓	✓	mg P/L, kg P/yr, mg N/L, kg N/L

Table S55. System boundary infosheet for beehives

Name of the NBS		Beehives	
NBS Typology		Use of fauna	
Description	A beehive is an enclosed structure man-made in which some honey bee species of the subgenus Apis live and raise their young.		
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Pollination of food and other plants ○ Increased crop yield ○ Honey 		N/A
Neighbourhood scale			
City scale			N/A

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Raw material efficiency	Food supply – of animal origin (O, N)	Urban farming, Transportation, Intensive farming	✓		pcs/d, pcs/yr, kg/yr, t/yr

Table S56. System boundary infosheet for insect hotels

Name of the NBS		Insect hotels	
NBS Typology		Use of fauna	
Description			
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	Noticeable effects due to <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Pollination, ○ Biodiversity, ○ Sound ecosystem. However it is hard to define quantifiable urban nexus for this NBS.		Harmful insects can also colonize.
Neighbourhood scale			N/A
City scale			N/A

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Material circularity indicator Raw material efficiency	Biomass (O)	Composting, Energy generation		✓	kg/m ³ /d, t/m ³ /yr, kg/m ² /yr, GJ/yr

Table S57. System boundary infosheet for use of grazing animals

Name of the NBS		Use of grazing animals	
NBS Typology		Use of fauna	
Description	Mulching is a technique used in plantations and maintenance that consists in covering the surface of the soil with an organic, mineral or plastic material in a continuous (film) or discontinuous way (grains, fragments, etc.) to protect the ground and plants mainly against weeds and soil evaporation. Originally, the term was created in 1935 to designate the action of mulching the soil (Loreau, 2014). In addition, mulching is one promising technology that is an integral component of conservation farming and is increasingly seen in the light of integrated soil management—an essential building stone for sustainable agriculture. The use of mulch has great agro-ecological potential—it typically conserves the soil, improves the soil ecology, stabilizes and enhances crop yield and provides various environmental services (Erenstein, 2003).		
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Maintain the level of biodiversity, ○ Sustainability, ○ Green economy, ○ Soil regeneration, ○ Soil management, ○ Restoration of degraded soils, ○ Productive lands, ○ Better conditions of the land, ○ Grazing may be implemented as a routine weeding method or to control invasive species 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Waste from animals and yards deterioration. ○ Methane emissions from animals
Neighbourhood scale			
City scale	N/A		N/A

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Avoided GHG emissions	GHG emissions released (O,vN)	All GHG emitting processes including combustion, Energy generation, Transportation, Biogenic and anthropogenic	✓		kg CO ₂ eq/yr, kg CO ₂ eq/kg of product
Cumulative energy demands	Energy demand for maintenance (O, N)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for soil treatment (O, N)				
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for maintenance (O, N)		✓		
	Energy demand for soil treatment (O, N)				
Per capita food production variability	Food supply - of animal origin (O)		✓		pcs/d, pcs/yr, kg/yr, t/yr
Raw material efficiency	Food supply - of animal origin (O, N)		✓		pcs/d, pcs/yr, kg/yr, t/yr

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
	Fertilizers – chemical (O, N)	Fertilizer manufacturing, Fertilizer transport, Fertilizer spreading	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Fertilizers – organic (O, N)				
	Herbicides – chemical (O, N)	Herbicides manufacturing, herbicides transport, Herbicide application			
	Herbicides – organic (O, N)				
	Herbicides avoided (O, N)				
Soil quality	Nutrients to soil (O, N)	Agricultural processes, Urban farming processes, Manufacturing industry, NBS maintenance		✓	kg/ha, g nutrient/kg soil, mg/L
Specific waste generation	Waste generated (C)	All waste generating processes	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr

Waste Management

Table S58. System boundary infosheet for composting

Name of the NBS		Composting	
Description		<p>Composting is a natural method for processing solid waste in which organic material is broken down by microorganisms in the presence of oxygen to a point where it can be safely stored, handled and applied to the environment as a fertilizer and soil amendment. Organic material has a twofold origin:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Community: urban allotments, small-scale urban livestock, nearby restaurants, markets, fruit stores, etc. – Industry processes: crops or agro-industry waste. <p>The objective is to close the loop on organics recovery. Likewise, this NBS has educational and engagement purposes. It could be helped by chickens because chickens clean the compost of weeds, rodents and insects, while the compost helps to warm the animals and feed the birds.</p>	
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Soil improvement potential but depends on the soil structure and organisms in the soil ○ Lower daily production of waste ○ Improved soil structure ○ Water and nutrient retainment ○ Improved crop yields and pastures ○ Plants with deeper root systems, healthy plants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Water for maintenance ○ Energy demand for maintenance and processing of waste 	
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Soil improvement potential but depends on the soil structure and organisms in the soil ○ Lower daily production of waste, "zero waste" production: loop-flows at neighbourhood scale (e.g. compost for communal gardens) ○ Recycling and use of recycled materials, value chain ○ Reduced pesticide and synthetic fertiliser use 	N/A	
City scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Soil improvement potential but depends on the soil structure and organisms in the soil ○ Lower daily production of waste ○ Recycling and use of recycled materials, value chain ○ Reduced pesticide and synthetic fertiliser use 	N/A	

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Cumulative energy demand	Compost (O, N)	Composting, Energy generation, Fuel consumption, Water consumption, Transportation	✓		kg/yr, t/yr
	Energy demand for processing of waste to be used as a resource (O)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Efficiency of valorisation as a result of recycling process	Waste recycled (N, C)	Recycling processes, Incineration process, Composting, Energy generation, Water pumping and treatment	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for maintenance (O)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for processing of waste to be used as a resource (O)				
Material circularity indicator	Waste recycled (N, C)	Recycling processes, Incineration process, Composting, Energy generation, Water pumping and treatment	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Raw material efficiency	Fertilizers avoided (N, C)	Fertilizer manufacturing, Fertilizer transport, Fertilizer spreading	✓	✓	kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Other resource (N, C)	All relevant processes producing or consuming resources not specified elsewhere in the list	✓	✓	kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Pesticides avoided (N, C)	Pesticide manufacturing, Pesticide transport, Pesticide application	✓	✓	kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
	Water for maintenance (O)	Pumping operations, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Soil quality	Organic matter content of soil (N, C)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/m ³
Specific waste generation	Waste generated (N, C)	All waste generating processes	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Water scarcity	Water for maintenance (O)	Pumping operations, Water treatment if necessary	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr

Protection and Conservation Strategies

Table S59. System boundary infosheet for limit or prevent some specific uses and practices

Name of the NBS		Limit or prevent some specific uses and practices	
Description	This NBS is the use of state regulations or community consensus. Through the implementation of this NBS certain areas can be preserved from intensive utilization or a resource efficient utilization can be emphasized. Master Plans or Local Building Acts define for example the ratio of construction within the building plot – if development is permissible – thus, green areas can be preserved by defining them as land which cannot be developed. Unlike to the NBS “Limit or prevent access to an area” this NBS concentrates on built-up areas of the city and its geographical scope remains within the administrative boundaries of the city.		
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Sustainable land use ○ Conserved and/or improved soil structure ○ Potential for aesthetics and biodiversity ○ Restricting use of water for preserving drinkable water resource ○ Restricting water pumping for preserving rivers water level 		N/A
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Restricting use of water for preserving drinkable water resource 		N/A
City scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Restricting water pumping for preserving rivers water level 		N/A

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Common air quality index	Air pollutants removed (O)	Direct capture by leaves, NOx and PM capture	✓		µg/ m ³ , mg/ m ³ , kg/year
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for water supply (O, N, C)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
Raw material efficiency	Water demand from supply system – for human consumption (O, N, C)	Water treatment, Pumping operation for water supply, Manufacturing and transportation of treatment chemicals, Energy generation, Disposal activities for treatment residues	✓		L/hr, L/d m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Water scarcity	Water demand from supply system – for human consumption (O, N, C)	Water treatment, Pumping operation for water supply, Manufacturing and transportation of treatment chemicals, Energy generation, Disposal activities for treatment residues	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr

Urban Planning Strategies

Table S60. System boundary infosheet for ensure continuity with ecological network

Name of the NBS		Ensure continuity with ecological network	
Description	This NBS contains the regulations, which can enable spatial connectivity between green spaces. The regulations make possible the use of different kinds of NBS that should be diverse as much as it can be to ensure the safe connectivity between wide green places. Usually the function of the linear elements of the network is only to give shelter to the fauna. Due to this NBS the biodiversity of the green places can be granted.		
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks ○ Capture atmospheric CO2 during natural lighting hours ○ Reducing the erosion caused by water runoff and increase in soil organic matter 		N/A
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nature and earth act as carbon sinks ○ Capture atmospheric CO2 during natural lighting hours ○ Reducing the erosion caused by water runoff and increase in soil organic matter 		N/A
City scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Sustainable land use ○ Aesthetics ○ Water reclamation potential ○ Biodiversity ○ Reducing the erosion caused by water runoff and increase in soil organic matter 		N/A

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Annual CO ₂ sequestration	Carbon sequestered (O, N, C)	Carbon uptake by plants		✓	kg CO ₂ eq/10 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq/100 yrs, kg CO ₂ eq per amount of biomass
Common air quality index	Air pollutants removed (O, N)	Direct capture by leaves, NO _x and PM capture	✓		µg/ m ³ , mg/ m ³ , kg/yr
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for cooling (O, N, C)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for water supply (O, N, C)				
Soil quality	Organic matter content of soil (O, N, C)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/m ³
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (N, C)	Wastewater treatment, manufacturing of chemicals, transportation of chemicals	✓		m ³ /yr

Table S61. System boundary infosheet for integration in the flooding map

Name of the NBS		Integration in the flooding map	
Description			
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Increased soil surface ○ Soil organisms ○ Water holding capacity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Water remediation ○ Biodiversity ○ Aesthetics ○ Reduced run-off ○ Reduced risk of flooding from rivers ○ Increased evapotranspiration ○ Improved water quality/reduced pollutants 	N/A
Neighbourhood scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Water remediation ○ Biodiversity 		N/A
City scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Aesthetics ○ Reduced run-off ○ Reduced risk of flooding from rivers ○ Increased evapotranspiration ○ Improved water quality/reduced pollutants 		N/A

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Soil quality	Organic matter content of soil (O,N,C)	All relevant processes releasing organic matter into the soil, Agricultural processes		✓	%, kg/m ³
Total runoff/total rainfall ratio	Stormwater avoided into the sewer (O,N,C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals	✓		m ³ /yr
	Surface runoff - not captured by stormwater sewers (O,N,C)	Wastewater treatment, Manufacturing of chemicals, Transportation of chemicals, All processes, All relevant processes utilizing the surface run-off if water reclamation is intended	✓		m ³ /d, m ³ /yr

Table S62. System boundary infosheet for limit use of agricultural land

Name of the NBS		Limit use of agricultural land	
Description			
Narrative impacts		Positive	Negative
Object scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Sustainable land use, ○ Conserved and/or improved soil structure, ○ Potential for aesthetics ○ Biodiversity 		Conventional methods may cause soil erosion or degradation
Neighbourhood scale			
City scale			

Indicator	Flows and applicable scales	Urban processes within the system boundaries	Operational cycle	Investment cycle	Unit of flow
Energy efficiency	Energy demand for construction (O)	Energy generation, Electricity production from renewable sources, Electricity production from non-renewable sources	✓		J, MJ, MJ/yr, kWh, kWh/hr, kWh/d, kWh/yr
	Energy demand for maintenance (O)				
	Energy demand for water supply (O)				
Raw material efficiency	Construction materials required (O)	Manufacturing of construction materials, Transportation construction materials	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Soil quality	Soil pollutants released (O, N, C)	All relevant processes generating soil pollutants	✓	✓	kg/m ³ , kg/m ³ /yr
Specific waste generation	Waste generated (O)	All waste generating processes	✓		kg/d, kg/yr, t/yr
Water quality	Water pollutants released (O)	All processes creating water pollutants	✓		L/hr, L/d, m ³ /d, m ³ /yr
Water scarcity	Water demand for irrigation (O)	Water pumping from groundwater, Energy generation, Water treatment if necessary	✓		m ³ /yr, in/h, mL/h